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Forest EcoValue

REPORT AND FACTSHEETS ON THE PARTICIPATORY PROCESS IN THE LIVING LABS (LLS)

D.2.1.1

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SO 2.2: Promoting the transition to a circular and resource efficient economy

Forest EcoValue:

**Supporting multiple forest ecosystem services through new
circular/green/bio markets and value chains**

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1. Introduction

This deliverable is delivered at month 37 of the Forest EcoValue project. This report defines the objectives, target audiences and users, tools and metrics for measuring the impact of the activities included in the participatory process.

Finpiemonte (PP1), with the specialised support of Walden S.r.l. and ERICA soc. coop., ensured continuous transnational coordination among the five Living Labs (hereinafter referred to as LLs), with the aim of steering the participatory process through a common approach and facilitating the exchange of good practices and challenges to enhance overall effectiveness.

Supervision of the Participatory Process (PP) has been ongoing since the initial phase of the pilot action and relied on continuous discussion and exchange regarding the strategies adopted in the five Living Lab areas to identify, contact, and involve stakeholders at local level.

PP1, with the specialised support of ERICA soc. coop., consistently provided assistance on the different aspects of the participatory process, fostering international exchange and mutual learning among the local coordinators.

ERICA soc. coop. arranged face-to-face meetings with the LL Coordinators and led discussion sessions and workshops on the local involvement strategies during the partner meetings in Graz, Austria (April 9th, 2024) and Ormea, Italy (October 22nd, 2024). The participation to the meeting in Munich (May 22nd, 2025) was ensured through a video summarizing the state of the art of the 5 LLs and highlighting the required actions from LL Coordinators. This was followed, in June/July 2025, by online bilateral and collective meetings involving the LLs Coordinators with the aim to better examine the progress made in the final phase of the participatory process. ERICA soc. coop. also supported the LL Coordinators in organising the intermediate and final local events and in compiling the customer satisfaction questionnaires.

Furthermore, the transnational coordination of the Living Labs was regularly included in the agenda of each project's monthly coordination meeting involving all partners.

Towards the conclusion of the participatory process, ERICA soc. coop. also interviewed each LL Coordinator with the purpose to identify the strengths and weaknesses points of the experience run in each territory.

2. Project overview

Forests of the Alpine Space play a key role in climate change mitigation and resilience, providing multiple ecosystem services (ES) and environmental and social benefits such as CO₂ absorption, air pollution reduction, biodiversity enhancement, and protection against natural hazards. However, they are threatened by abandonment, climate change, and territorial degradation, which progressively reduce natural resources and the provision of forest ES (FES). Maintenance costs of Alpine forests are high, and public funds and traditional wood value chains are insufficient to cover them. Economic valuation and payment schemes for FES are widely discussed but rarely successfully applied.

The Forest EcoValue project addresses this challenge by developing innovative, sustainable business models for forest management and maintenance, supporting new bio-based value chains and ES markets, and involving different sectors, public and private actors, and citizens. Restoring and maintaining healthy forests has been recognised as a source of value for the Alpine region, while also creating business opportunities and green jobs for Alpine communities.

The project focuses on a subset of FES from the following categories:

- **Provisioning** (e.g. biomass, raw materials, chemicals) with a specific focus on non-timber forest products, and on the production of woody biomass for energy, integrated into circular energy markets.
- **Regulating** (e.g. biodiversity, natural risk reduction, CO₂ absorption) concretely working on carbon and biodiversity credits, natural risk management through protective forests, and innovative environmental finance instruments such as green bonds and reverse auctions.
- **Cultural** (e.g. recreation, habitat experience, health) particularly enhancing recreational and tourism services and spiritual and cultural services.

These services have been explored and tested within Living Labs (LLs) across five countries, located in different Alpine territories and representing diverse ecological and socio-economic contexts:

- **Italy – Valle Tanaro, Piedmont:** The LL in Valle Tanaro explores innovative approaches to valorising chestnut groves, promoting non-timber forest products, developing carbon and biodiversity credits, and fostering experiential activities linked to forest and rural heritage.
- **France - Haute-Savoie:** Grand Annecy and Thonon LLs focus respectively on two aspects 1) recreational ecosystem services, enhancing the value of forests through the sale of experiences such as ecotourism, outdoor activities, and educational programmes 2) enhancing the value of water regulation services through a public-private partnership.
- **Slovenia – Karavanke Mountains, municipality Tržič:** The Slovenian LL addresses natural risk management with a focus on torrent control, advances solutions for wood biomass supply chains and promotes sustainable tourism and recreational use of forests.
- **Austria – Province of Styria:** The Styrian LL concentrates on biodiversity and habitat provision and stabilizing the carbon cycle in the forest ecosystem (carbon sequestration and storage) through innovative financing mechanisms such as reverse auctions.
- **Germany – Bavarian Prealps, Upper Bavaria:** The German Living Lab explores spiritual and cultural services, such as burial forests with biodegradable urns, while also examining the feasibility of a green initiative to offer nature education and awareness raising events (“forest lobbying”) about the multifunctionality of the forest.

Accordingly, the project is aiming to:

- Map and analyse the Alpine Space forests delivery capacity of FES;
- Identify and estimate the economic potential, define business models and FES market frameworks;
- Test the models/tools developed by the consortium in pilot LLs involving local players;
- Compare results at transnational level, identifying obstacles and facilitating factors;
- Analyse the need for innovative policies to foster forest maintenance, FES markets, and new value chains;
- Elaborate refined transferable tools/models and policy proposals to enable new markets

and value chains and ensure the expected FES.

Throughout the project, a continuous participatory process is carried out within the Living Labs. Stakeholders' active involvement in these labs is essential for co-designing and testing models and tools, ensuring that the innovative approaches are rooted in local realities. In parallel, public events and capacity-building workshops have strengthened engagement, supported knowledge transfer, and provided regular updates on project activities. This participatory and long-term approach, tested across the five territories, is paving the way for refined, transferable tools and policy proposals that can unlock new markets and value chains while safeguarding the provision of ecosystem services in the Alpine Space.

Project duration: 42 months.

3. PART 1 – Report per Living Lab area

In the following chapter, the Participatory Process implemented in each of the five Living Labs is described, together with the indicators that emerged from the analysis of the inputs collected from LL Coordinators through the following tools:

- LL descriptions;
- Interviews with LL Coordinators;
- Minutes of the meetings with stakeholders;
- Stakeholder lists divided into target groups;
- Stakeholder maps and matrixes;
- Stakeholder satisfaction surveys;
- Press releases.

3.1 Living Lab presentation

In the next paragraphs, in synthesis, the 5 LLs are described from a geographical point of view, with a focus on the forest areas and on characteristics relevant for the Participatory Process and the definition of Forest Ecosystem Services (FES).

3.1.1 Austria

Geographical location

The Living Lab in Styria is primarily located in the central region of Austria, characterized by its rich forest ecosystems and diverse land use practices. Styria, known for its mountainous terrain and extensive woodlands, is situated in southeastern Austria, bordered by the provinces of Upper Austria, Lower Austria, Burgenland, Salzburg, Carinthia, and Slovenia.

17 Forest Owners, whose applications for participation were accepted, have their forest properties located in 14 municipalities and nine districts: Langenwang municipality in Bruck-Mürzzuschlag district (15 applications in total), Sankt Stefan ob Stainz municipality in Deutschlandsberg district (one application in total), Fürstenfeld, Sankt Lorenzen am Wechsel and Waldbach-Mönichwald municipalities in Hartberg-Fürstenfeld district (four applications in total), Kammern im Liesingtal municipality in Leoben district

(one application in total), St. Peter am Kammersberg and Murau municipalities in Murau district (five applications in total), Sankt Margarethen bei Knittelfeld municipality in Murtal district (four applications in total), Fehring municipality in Südoststeiermark district (three applications in total), Geistthal-Södingberg municipality in Voitsberg district, and Birkfeld, Gasen and Thannhausen municipalities in Weiz district (11 applications in total). One application was impossible to locate.

Map of the macro region with districts (boxes present municipalities where the participating forest properties are located).

Figure 1: Overview map of the microregion with districts (<https://gis.stmk.gv.at/wgportal/atlasmobile/map/Basiskarten/Kataster>).

Land use

In Styria, land use is primarily divided among the following categories:

- **Forests:** Approximately 61% of Styria's land area is covered by forests, making it the most forested region in Austria.
- **Agricultural Land:** About 33% of the land is used for agriculture, primarily for crop and livestock production.
- **Urban Areas:** Cities and towns account for around 10% of the land, with Graz being the largest urban center.

Topography and climate

Styria has a temperate continental climate characterized by warm summers and cold winters. The region experiences significant seasonal variations in temperature and precipitation. The average temperature in the capital of Styria (Graz) is 9,8 degrees Celsius. Mean annual average precipitation is about **900–2,000 mm** per year, depending on the elevation. The elevation ranges from around **200 m** in the lowland areas to over **2,000 m** in the mountainous regions.

Geology and pedology

The region consists mainly of the Northern Limestone Alps, featuring a diverse geological landscape, including limestone, dolomite, and sedimentary rocks. Prevailing soil types are predominantly clay, loam, and sandy soils, with fertile agricultural soils in valley areas and less fertile soils on steep slopes. The groundwater table varies significantly, generally lying between **1–5 meters** below the surface but can be deeper in mountainous areas.

Organisational structure

The **Styria Forestry Directorate** oversees forestry management in the region, implementing national policies and ensuring sustainable practices. Local municipalities also play a role in forest management and land-use planning.

Various associations exist to represent private and communal Forest Owners, providing support, resources, and advocacy for sustainable forestry practices. The main one is “Waldverband Steiermark”. Local authorities manage municipal forests, enforce land use regulations, and facilitate community involvement in forestry initiatives.

Ownership

Approximately **53% of forests** in Styria are privately owned, **35% are public**, and the remaining **12% are owned by municipalities**. The average size of privately-owned forest properties in the region is around **5–10 hectares**, with larger holdings often found among public and communal lands.

Ownership goals focus on promoting sustainable forest management practices, increasing biodiversity, and enhancing forest resilience to climate change.

Description of stand characteristics in the pilot area

Approximately **60%** of the land in Styria is covered by forests, with a significant portion of this land falling within the Living Lab area.

The distribution of tree species is roughly **31% deciduous** (e.g., oak, beech) and **69% coniferous** (e.g., spruce, fir).

The most common species in the growing stock include:

- Spruce (59%)
- Beech (8%)
- Larch (6%)

The density of mixed forests is approximately **70%**, while pure forests, primarily dominated by a single species like spruce, account for around **30%**.

- Stock composition

Styria’s forests typically exhibit a multi-layered structure, including:

- **Overstory:** Dominated by mature trees.
- **Understory:** Comprising younger trees and shrubs.

About **40%** of the forest area consists of natural forest communities, which include a mix of indigenous tree species.

The predominant forest types are:

- **Montane forests:** ~50%
- **Subalpine forests:** ~30%

- **Lowland forests:** ~20%

The average growing stock is estimated at **200–300 m³/ha**. The mean annual increment is around **6–10 m³/ha**.

The age distribution of forests in the area (% of forest area) is as follows:

- **Even-aged regeneration:** ~25%
- **Even-aged intermediate:** ~30%
- **Even-aged mature:** ~20%
- **Uneven-aged:** ~25%

The presence of deadwood is crucial for biodiversity. Standing deadwood constitutes about **10%** of the forest biomass.

The average annual logging rate is approximately **10–15 m³/ha**, depending on local management practices. Certain tree species are well-suited to the varying soil and climatic conditions in Styria, with species like spruce and beech being favoured for timber production.

- Map of forests

Common forest management techniques include:

- Young stand and juvenile stand maintenance.
- Thinning to promote growth and health of remaining trees.
- Regeneration systems: Both natural regeneration and replanting are employed.
- Forest establishment: This includes both plantations and promoting natural rejuvenation.

Infrastructure in the pilot area

The density of roads in forest areas varies, with primary access routes in more populated areas. Forest road density is approximately **100–150 m/ha**, facilitating access for management and logging. There are

several sawmills and wood processing facilities located near major forested areas, supporting local economies.

Forest products in the pilot area

About **60%** of forest area is used for wood production, including:

- Timber
- Pulpwood
- Fuelwood

Approximately **20%** of the forest area provides non-wood goods, such as:

- Mushrooms
- Berries
- Medicinal plants

Hunting in the pilot area

Hunting in Styria is organized through local associations, which manage hunting rights and quotas. Common species include deer, wild boar, and various game birds, with regulated hunting quotas established annually.

Protected areas & nature conservation in the pilot area

The region contains several protected areas, including:

- Nature conservation areas
- Landscape protection areas
- Natura 2000 sites

Approximately **15%** of the Living Lab area is designated as protected.

Natural hazard protection in the pilot area

Forests play a critical role in natural hazard protection, particularly against:

- Avalanches
- Mudslides
- Flooding

Recreation and tourism in the pilot area

Styria offers a range of recreational activities, including hiking, mountain biking, and skiing.

- Hiking and mountain bike trails have a density of approximately **5–10 m/ha**.
- The area has numerous recreational cabins, with a density of about **0.5–1 m²/ha**.
- Skiing is popular, with several ski lifts and facilities concentrated in the higher elevations.
- There are regional forest playgrounds and adventure centers, as well as forest related education centers.

Other characteristics and specifics of the pilot area

Styria has a rich cultural history related to forestry, including traditional forest pasture management practices and historical timber rights that continue to influence land use today.

3.1.2 France

Geographical location

The French Living Lab is in the Grand Annecy area, Haute-Savoie department, in the Auvergne–Rhône-Alpes region. It includes the city of Annecy and 33 surrounding municipalities, covering about 515 km². The area lies within the northern French Pre-Alps, around Lake Annecy (27 km²), situated between the Geneva basin and the alpine valleys. Elevations range from approximately 396 m in the valley to over 1,500 m on surrounding peaks.

The LL includes: Annecy (which incorporates Annecy-le-Vieux, Cran-Gevrier, Meythet, Seynod, and Pringy), Alby-sur-Chéran, Allèves, Argonay, Bluffy, Chainaz-les-Frasses, Chapeiry, Charvonnex, Chavanod, Cusy, Duingt, Entrevernes, Epagny Metz-Tessy, Fillière (including Aviernois, Évires, Les Ollières, Saint-Martin-Bellevue, and Thorens-Glières), Groisy, Gruffy, Héry-Sur-Alby, La Chapelle-Saint-Maurice, Leschaux, Menthon-Saint-Bernard, Montagny-les-Lanches, Mûres, Nâves-Parmelan, Poisy, Quintal, Saint-Eustache, Saint-Félix, Saint-Jorioz, Saint-Sylvestre, Sevrier, Sillingy, Talloires-Montmin, Veyrier-du-Lac, Villaz and Viuz-la-Chiésaz.

Figure 3: Overview map of the LL's territory in France.

Land use

Land use is separated between an urban core around Annecy and lake shores and surrounding with agricultural and forested zones and other natural landscapes.

Forests covers 23,000 ha in Grand Annecy with public and communal forests (managed by ONF) representing 42% and private forests (supported by CNPF) 58%. Ownership is thus roughly balanced between public and private sectors, with key forest areas including Semnoz-Val Laudon, Tournette-Veyrier and Parmelan-Glières.

Geomorphology and climate

Grand Ancey occupies a montane basin influenced by Lake Annecy and surrounding mountains (Semnoz, Parmelan, La Tournette). The climate is montane with cold winters, frequent snow at higher altitudes, and warm, humid summers (less with climate change). Mean annual temperature is about 9.5 °C, and annual precipitation averages 1,600–1,650 mm. Elevations vary from 396 m to over 1,500 m (Tournette being the highest point at 2,351 m), producing significant ecological diversity.

The area belongs to the French Pre-Alps, composed mainly of limestone and marls from the Mesozoic era. Valleys and lake basins contain glacial and alluvial deposits from the Quaternary period. Soils near the lake are alluvial or lacustrine, while mountain slopes have shallow calcareous soils. Groundwater levels vary seasonally, shallow in valleys and deep in karstic formations of the limestone mountains.

Description of stand characteristics in the pilot area

Altitudes range from 400 m to 1,900 m for forest cover, encompassing three vegetation belts:

- Valley and hillside zone: deciduous (oak, beech, chestnut, hornbeam)
- Montane zone: mixed and coniferous (fir, spruce, beech) between 800m and 1,200m
- Subalpine zone: spruce-dominated forests to 1,900m

Deciduous stands represent ~65–70%, conifers 25–30%. Dominant species include beech, oak, fir, and spruce. Most stands are two-layered with mixed-age structures, and natural forests represent 70–80% of the forest area. Average growing stock is 300–350 m³/ha, with an annual increment of 6–7 m³/ha and an annual harvest below this level (around 4–5 m³/ha). Deadwood is increasingly present due to beetle outbreaks.

Management varies with altitude and ownership. Public forests near urban areas serve protective and recreational functions, while mountain forests are managed for multifunctionality (protection, timber, biodiversity). Management increasingly emphasizes natural regeneration, mixed species composition, and irregular stand structures. Spruce monocultures are declining due to drought and pest vulnerability. Harvests prioritize selective cutting, cluster management on steep slopes, and maintaining continuous cover to reduce climatic stress.

Figure 4: Overview map of the distribution of forests and their typology in France.

Protected areas and nature conservation

Grand Annecy hosts diverse protection designations:

- Nature Reserves: Bout du Lac (84 ha), Roc de Chère (64 ha)
- Natura 2000 sites: Albanais wetlands, Cluse du Lac d'Annecy, Frettes–Glières, La Tournette (10,000 ha total)
- ENS (Sensitive Natural Areas): 41 sites
- ZNIEFF: 55 sites (6000 ha Type I, 27,000 ha Type II)
-

Natural hazard protection

Forests play an essential role in mitigating natural hazards, notably rockfalls, landslides, and floods. The steep pre-alpine slopes pose risks of ground movement; protective forests cover about 462,000 m² near inhabited zones. Vegetation intercepts falling boulders and reduces impact energy, providing natural protection for numerous buildings and infrastructure.

Recreation, education and tourism

Lake Annecy and its surrounding mountains attract significant tourism. Outdoor activities include hiking, cycling, mountain biking, skiing, and water sports. The area hosts over 36000 participants annually across major trail events. The region contains around 552 km of trails and 190 ha of skiable terrain (Semnoz, Glières). Environmental education and awareness programs are run by local associations and public agencies to balance recreation and conservation.

3.1.3 Germany

Geographical location

The Living Lab is situated in the administrative districts Munich, Miesbach, Bad Tölz-Wolfratshausen and Garmisch-Partenkirchen in the Bavarian Prealps. The Living Lab consists of 5 sub-areas. The areas Endlhausen, Sauerlach, Buchberg and Gstaig belong to the Archdiocese Munich and Freising (Living Lab 1), whereas the forest nearby Waakirchen belongs to the private forest owner L.B. (Living Lab 2).

Figure 5: Overview map of the Living Lab areas (© 2025 basemap.de).

Land use

The forest occupies the largest proportion of the pilot area with **53%** followed by agricultural land with **26%**. The forest is mainly located in the highlands, whereas the lowlands are characterized by agricultural use.

Topography and climate

The pilot area is mainly within the moist-continental climate zone. With warm summers, cold winters and consistent precipitation throughout the year. The area spans two main Bavarian climate regions: the

Alpine Foothills (**53%**) and portions of the Northern Limestone Alps (**47%**). The Alps experience higher precipitation and lower temperatures compared to the Foothills.

Geology and pedology

The geology is predominantly characterized by Rhenodanubian Flysch, specifically the Lower Variegated Marl (Oferschwanger Layers) up to the Anthering Formation. The predominant soil type is Brown Earth or Para-Brown Earth, covering more than half of the Living Lab area. Gley and Pseudogley soils are the second most common.

Ownership

Living Lab area 1 belongs to the Archdiocese Munich-Freising, a large ecclesiastical organization that places significant emphasis on ethical questions and sustainable forest management. Fragmented Forest Ownership is characteristic for the Archdioceses holdings. **Living Lab area 2** in the municipality of Waakirchen is owned by the private forest owner L.B.

The forest in the Living lab covers a total area of **441.17 ha**.

Forest management

The forest areas of the Archdiocese (Living Lab 1) are in the Endlhausen district and are divided into 4 sub-areas: The **Endlhausen** area has a total of 27.55 ha of commercial forest. The **Sauerlach** forest area has a total of 116,37 ha. The **Buchberg** area, which is located west of the city Geretsried has a total of 72,87 ha of commercial forest area and the fourth area at **Gstaig** has a total of 100,32 ha of commercial forests. The forest area is mainly characterized by spruce forests of all ages. However, some forest areas also feature deciduous forests or mixed deciduous forests, such as Buchberg, which got its name from the presence of beech forests. The forests of the Archdiocese are primarily subject to sustainable management practices and thus in accordance with the silvicultural objectives of the Archdiocese of Munich-Freising. Since the stands mainly consist of even-aged or two-storied age-class forests, appropriate silvicultural measures are applied for the respective age classes. Management of the forest area is carried out by the district forest manager. Thinning operations, planting, timber extraction, and timber transport are performed by subcontractors.

The forest areas at **Waakirchen**, owned by private landowner L.B., cover approximately 279.13 hectares, of which about 124.06 hectares are forest land and the rest is non-forest land, primarily used as alpine pasture. The forest itself is a typical mountainous mixed forest composed of spruce, beech, and fir, with coniferous species dominating. The stands are characterized by their multi-layered structure and diverse species mixture. All age classes are represented evenly throughout the area. Most of the thinning and tending operations are carried out by the owner himself, with the support of external timber contractors. Forest management as well as timber marketing and transportation are carried out by the Forest Owners' Association Holzkirchen.

The goals of both Forest Owners are continuous timber production, promotion of healthy and stable forests, recreation and education, promotion of biodiversity, nature conservation, and climate protection.

Protected areas & nature conservation

Categories of protected areas in the Living Lab area:

- Landscape conservation areas (LSG);
- Natura 2000 areas (FFH areas and special protection areas (SPA));
- Biotopes.

In particular, a significant portion of the forest at **Waakirchen** owned by L.B. lies within a landscape conservation area (241.3 ha) which is named "Egartenlandschaft um Miesbach". In addition, the forest area borders to the east on the FFH area "Flyschberge bei Bad Wiessee" (ID 8236-371). A part of the east located forest areas at **Sauerlach** sub area lay within a landscape conservation area ("LSG Otterfing - Hofoldingner Forst"). To the east, in the immediate vicinity, is the „LSG Hofoldingner und Höhenkirchner Forst“ landscape conservation area. The **Gstaig** forest area lies partly within the FFH area "Murnauer Moos" (ID 8332-301) and the Special Protection Area "Murnauer Moos and Pfruehlmoos" (ID 8332-471). To the south, the **Gstaig** area borders the Natura 2000 site "Extensive Meadows around Glentleiten bei Großweil" (ID 8333-371) The Living Lab also contains several biotopes, mainly wet meadows, moors or species-rich grasslands under extensive use.

Natural hazard protection

In **Living Lab 2 (Waakirchen)** the risk for natural hazards is increased. Slope fractures within and outside of forest are a hazard in 57% of Living Lab 2. Landslides potentially occur in over 34% and deep landslides in nearly 16% of the area. Rockfall is only a small risk and could occur in 1.6% of the area (Notably, there are no avalanche lines within the pilot area (LfU 2025d). To prevent these hazards there are some forests with special benefits and legal status. Avalanche protection forest cover over 8% of the area and forests to protect the soil cover more than 90% of the Living Lab. Protective forests in accordance with Art. 10 BayWaldG cover over 35% of the forest area (LWF 2025). In **Living Lab 1 (Gstaig)**, there is a small area within the forest that is prone to landslides.

Recreation and tourism

The greater region between the Alps and Munich, where the Living Labs are situated, offers a diverse range of recreational and tourism activities rooted in its natural beauty. Visitors can enjoy an extensive network of hiking and walking trails, as well as cycling and mountain biking routes suitable for all skill levels. In winter, skiing, snowboarding, and winter hiking are available in nearby locations. The forest areas are located not far from major urban centers, such as the Munich metropolitan area, the town of Bad Tölz, and the town of Geretsried.

Parts of the forest area in the **Sauerlach** district and in **Waakirchen** are located in functional forest for recreation in accordance with Art. 6 of the Bavarian Forest Act 2 (LWF 2025).

3.1.4 Italy

Geographical location

The Italian Living Lab is located in the south of the Piedmont region, bordering the Liguria region and France. The LL's surface covers 67.264 ha, and corresponds to the Forest Area 13, which includes Langa Cebana hills, Mongia, Cevetta and Upper Tanaro valleys. Alta Valle Tanaro is the main valley of this area, in terms of surface.

The LL includes 30 municipalities: Priero, Bagnasco, Marsaglia, Alto, Rocca Cigliè, Nucetto, Murazzano, Montezemolo, Briga Alta, Battifollo, Scagnello, Mombasiglio, Perlo, Ceva, Ormea, Garessio, Roascio, Viola, Castellino Tanaro, Paroldo, Cigliè, Caprauna, Sale San Giovanni, Torresina, Lesegno, Priola, Castelnuovo

di Ceva, Lisio, Igliano, Sale delle Langhe.

Figure 6: Overview map of the Living Lab's municipalities.

Land use

The forest cover represents most of the total area, and it's mainly distributed in the mountain areas, while on the hillside area the land use is mostly dedicated to agriculture, especially to vineyards and hazelnut orchards.

Geomorphology and climate

The area under consideration is characterized by a prevailing rainfall pattern of type Sublitoraneo, with minimum main in summer, maximum main in autumn and maximum secondary in spring. Most of the solid precipitation occurs during the first three months of the year, between January and March, and the time of permanence of the snow cover is on average 3 - 4 months a year. One phenomenon that occurs with a certain frequency is late snowfall.

The elevation range of the LL is influenced by the presence of the Tanaro River, so that the lowest elevation sites are found by the riverbed and in the south-west part of the area, while the highest

elevation reach 550 m a.s.l. on the northern peaks.

The Tanaro Valley geological units have a long history of Alpine polyphasic deformation, which has resulted in a very complex structural arrangement. Soil types that can be found in the LL vary from very shallow and undeveloped soils in the most disturbed areas to deeper and developed into the paedogenetic process.

Description of stand characteristics in the pilot area

The total forest cover of the LL is 41,358 ha, which represents 61% of the total area. Deciduous species largely prevail on conifers: forest types based on conifers composition represent around 7% of the forest cover, and around 93% of the mountain belt reforestation areas, for a total of 3,451 ha. Therefore, approximately the conifers cover around 12% of the total forest cover, while deciduous species prevail with 88% of forest cover.

Table 1: Forest types and related data in the Italian LL

Main forest categories	Surface (ha)	Basal area (m ² /ha)	Volume (m ³ /ha)	Relative increment (m ³ /ha/year)
Chestnut	18,812	35	186 (of which around 50% is dead biomass)	6.8
Chestnut	18,812	35	186 (of which around 50% is dead biomass)	6.8
Beech	8,723	28	166	5.2
Hop hornbeam	2,744	15	65	3.8
Downy oak	3,194	113	433	5.0

Figure 7: Overview map of the forest categories in the Italian LL.

Protected areas & nature conservation

Categories of protected areas are: Nature Conservation areas, Banned Forest, Landscape Protection areas, Natura 2000, FFH areas and others.

In the LL there are some registered Natura 2000 areas: Natural Parks (Parco del Maraguis), ZSC/SIC and ZPS areas (fraction of the ZSC/ZPS Alte Valli Pesio e Tanaro area, Alto Caprauna, Monte Antorotto), SIR (Grotta dell'Orso), natural reserves (fraction of the Riserva Naturale delle Sorgenti del Belbo).

All the protected areas occupy more than 17% of the pilot area.

Natural hazard protection

Related to the protection against avalanches, mud slides, rock falls or floods, the 14% of the LL's forest cover is managed as direct protection forest, the majority of which is represented by beech coppice forests. While avalanches don't expose the LL to a particularly urgent risk, disturbances that involve mudslides and floods are quite frequent and can be mitigated with an adequate forest management strategy.

Recreation, education and tourism

Recreation and tourism activities in the LL are based on the accessibility of the forest area, that offers the chance to enjoy the inheritance value of the valley and the mountain chain, but they're also based on the local agronomic tradition, that attract tourists especially from Liguria and Piemonte, thanks for the

agricultural landscape and culinary tradition. Chestnut and hazelnut orchards are typical elements of Tanaro Valley's slope and low-mountain areas.

The main sport and recreational activities can be identified in hiking and cycling (169,157 m. l. of cycling tracks of regional interest); the agrotourism field is also active, as some new receptive structures were created or enhanced during the last few decades. A secondary activity, fishing, is also practiced in some municipalities, for example Ormea, by both locals and tourists.

The Tanaro Valley offers a unique academic education program on forestry and environmental issues thanks to the Forestry School of Ormea, which is the only Italian public school that guarantees this kind of professional apprenticeship on high school level.

3.1.5 Slovenia

Geographical location

Slovene Living Lab (LL) is the Municipality of Tržič in northern Slovenia, covering an area of 15,500 hectares.

Figure 8: Location of LL – municipality Tržič in Slovenia.

Figure 9: Municipality Tržič with elevations (a.s.l.).

Land use

73% of the municipality's area is covered by forests, agricultural land is mainly located in the southern lowland part, with some alpine pastures also present. The largest settlement is Tržič, with about 3,000 inhabitants, while the entire municipality has around 15,000 residents living in 35 settlements — approximately 98 inhabitants per km².

Topography and climate

The municipality lies at the foot of the Karawanks mountain range. Its northern part is mountainous, with the highest peak reaching 2,133 m, gradually descending southward into hilly terrain and then into flat river-glacial terraces, with the lowest point at 424 m. The average elevation is 1,080 m, and the average slope is 25.3°. The climate is alpine, characterized by high precipitation — the average annual rainfall in Tržič is about 1,400 mm, and in higher areas it exceeds 1,700 mm.

Geology and pedology

The municipality has a diverse geological and soil composition. In the mountainous areas, carbonate rocks prevail, mainly Triassic limestones and dolomites. The hilly region features more varied geology, including Carboniferous, Permian, and Triassic rocks such as sandstones, shales, conglomerates, breccias, limestones, dolomites, keratophyres, and porphyries. In the lowlands, glaciofluvial sediments dominate. Soil conditions also change rapidly. The most common soils are rendzinas, followed by dystric and eutric brown soils, with occurrences of leached soils, rankers, hypogleys, and alluvial soils. The municipality is rich in watercourses, the largest being the Tržiška Bistrica, Mošenik, and Lomščica rivers.

Organizational structure

The entire LL area falls within a single municipality, the Municipality of Tržič.

Slovenia Forest Service (SFS, “Zavod za gozdove Slovenije”) is responsible for forest management and prepares forest management plans for all forest in Slovenia, public and private. The LL area falls under SFS regional unit Kranj and SFS local unit Tržič. There are 5 SFS districts (Podljubelj, Košuta, Vetrlih, Lom, Kovor); in each of them there is a district forester employed. There are some organizations, contenting Forest Owners; for us, the most important are the Forest owner association of Gorenjska and the Forest owner association of Upper Gorenjska. Important organization in the field of forestry is also “Slovenski državni gozdovi d.o.o.” company’s (SiDG, Slovenian state forest company) purpose is to manage the state forests according to the management plans in state forests.

Ownership

Private forests prevail, accounting for 85.5% of the total forest area, while 9.7% are state-owned and 4.7% are municipal forests. Average forest property in LL is 0.5 ha, more than 2000 forest (co)owners. Despite high number of owners, there are quite some owners with large properties (Figure 3).

Figure 10: 1Number of Forest Owners per property category

Description of stand characteristics in the pilot area

- Forest cover: 11.290 ha, 72.7%
- Tree species composition (% of growing stock): Norway spruce 60.0%, European beech 21.4%, silver fir 8.1%, nobel broadleaves 2.2%, hard broadleaves 1.6%, larch 3.7%, pine ssp. 1.3%, oak ssp. 1.1%
- Mixed forests 63.6% and pure forests 36.4 % (stands are considered as pure if there is more than 75% of one species in basal area)
- Prevailing forest types (%): montane and alpine beech forests, mixed spruce, silver-fir beech forests on silicate and on carbonate protective forests, spruce forests
- Average growing stock: 401 m³/ha
- Average increment: 7.87 m³/ha
- Average annual cut 5.03 m³/ha, allowable cut 7.19 m³/ha
- Development phases (% of forest area):
 - Even-aged stands under regeneration 14.8%
 - Even-aged pole stand 11.3%
 - Even-aged mature stand 64.2%
 - Young growth 9.7%
- Deadwood: 20 pieces/ha standing and 20 pieces/ha felled deadwood, altogether 26.7 m³/ha
- Naturalness of forest communities (%): There are big differences in two FMUs, Jeledol and Tržič. in northern part – (FMU Jelendol) forests are relative changed, whereas in southern part (FMU Tržič) the tree composition is more preserved. In the LL there are 37.7% preserved, 40.2% changed, 17.3% heavily changed and 4.7% altered forests.

Table 2: Forest types in Slovenian LL

Forest type	Percentage (%)
Subalpine and montane beech forests	20.4
Subalpine mixed spruce, silver-fir, beech forests on carbonate	18.7
Protective forest	16.5
Subalpine mixed spruce, silver-fir beech forests on silicate	12.0
Spruce forests	10.1
Forest with a special purpose	6.6
Acidophilous beech forests	5.4
Silver-fir forests	4.4
Thermophilous beech forests	2.1
Submontane beech forests	1.6
Acidophilous beech forests	1.2
Pine forests	0.6
Riparian vegetation	0.5

Forest management techniques in the pilot area

For Slovenia, and LL, tradition of close to nature forest management (prohibition of clear cuts, based on natural regeneration, mimicking natural disturbance regimes) based on forest management plans. The prevailing management systems in LL are irregular shelter wood, group selection system ("Femelschlag"). Average forest stand size in LL is 3.7 ha. Especially in northern part of LL, forest management unit (FMU) Jelendol, the legacy of previous management is visible and spruce monocultures prevail at bigger scale. Regeneration is mostly of natural origin under the old stand, in the shelter of mature trees where patches are

0.5 to 1.5 of tree heights (depends on site conditions and regeneration goals). Regeneration is finished in two to three circles (for example 30 % of volume, 50 % of volume, all trees) and it last approximately from 10 to 30 years (depends on site and stand conditions and management goals). Later patches are aggregated together. There is some complementary regeneration and some artificial planting (0.02% of forest area), mainly with spruce and beech. Selection of trees for cutting/marketing the trees is obligatory for all forests. Tending is planned for younger stand. For most of forest types the rotation periods are 120-160 years long and for pine forests and riparian forests 110 years long. Final growing stock for protective forests is 380 m³/ha, for most of the forest types it ranges from 500 to 700m³/ha.

Forestry had always been important in the LL. Currently Forest management faces several challenges. One of the challenges is less active forest management, especially in protective forests, of which there are many in the area due to the terrain. If these are not managed, the stability and vitality of the stands decrease, the stands age and regeneration is insufficient. Another challenge is related to areas where spruce was promoted in the past; these areas are more vulnerable to windbreaks and bark beetle attacks.

Infrastructure in the pilot area

Density of public roads is 2.7 m/ha, density of forest roads is 11.9 m/ha and density of logging roads and skid trails 44.9 m/ha. There are many small loggings and harvesting enterprises in the LL, two woodchips companies, one of which is also active in the wood processing industry. An important market for wood is Austria.

Forest products in the pilot area

Forestry had always been an important activity in the LL, as had the gathering of non-wood products. The forest management plans FES provision of wood is emphasised on 54.8% of forest area and provision of non-timber forest goods on 1.2% of forest area.

Hunting in the pilot area

Organisation of hunting in Slovenia: Legislation about wildlife animals is divided in legislation for game species and legislation for protective species which are under Ministry of agriculture, forestry and food and Ministry of the environment and spatial planning, respectively. Owner of all wild animals is Republic of Slovenia. Forest-owners must allow hunting on their ground. The right to hunt is therefore independent from the ownership right to land. This is established in the Forest Act of 1993, where it is said that even if private rights should be fully respected, "the rights of ownership to forests shall be exercised in such a manner as ensures their ecological, social, and productive functions". Forest should be managed considering whole ecosystem, not just its parts. That is why SFS is making hunting plans for

hunting management regions. Our LL is located in “Gorenjsko “management region. There are several hunting management units (LD) inside hunting management region; in our LL: LD Tržič, part of LD Dobrča and part of LD Udenboršt. In hunting management units hunters are voluntarily included. There is also part of a special hunting management unit (LPN) within our LL; LPN Kozorog Kamnik. Special hunting management units are under management of SFS, where professional hunters are employed.

Species and number of hunted preys:

Plan of removal for game species in « Gorenjsko » regional management unit for 2022 (number of pieces per 1000 ha of per year):

- Red deer (*Cervus elaphus*) 4.3
- Roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*) 18.9
- Wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) 1.4
- Ibex (*Capra ibex*) only ill animals (maximum 2)
- Chamois (*Rupicapra rupicapra*) 2.9
- Hare (*Lepus europaeus*) 1.1
- Fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) 6.5
- European badger (*Meles meles*) 0.7
- European pine marten and beech marten (*Martes martes*, *Martes foina*) 0.9
- Alpine marmot (*Marmota marmota*) 0.07
- European mouflon (*Ovis ammon musimon*) 0.3

Protected areas & nature conservation in the pilot area

Natura 2000 areas cover more than 86% of forests in LL (only forest without *Pinus mugo*). The important areas are: “Karavanke”, “Ročevnica” in “Dacarjevo brezno– Žiganja vas”. The Dovžan Gorge is natural monument due to the remains of plant and animal life preserved in rocks from the Paleozoic era.

Natural hazard protection in the pilot area

16.5 % of the forests are protective forests.

Recreation and tourism in the pilot area

Due to its proximity to larger cities (35 minutes from Ljubljana, 20 minutes from Kranj), the area is attractive for day trips. Tourist attractions include the natural monument of the Dovžan Gorge, the St Anne Mine, the Ljubelj/Mauthausen concentration camp, and Tekec nativity scene. The forest area is place for several types of recreation; the area is particularly interesting for hikers, cyclists and ski tourers. Zelenica and Star Ljubelj are among the most visited areas.

3.2 Participatory process and stakeholders' analysis

The Participatory Process is primarily based on the active involvement of the stakeholders in the project activities at different levels.

Given the diversity of the Forest Ecosystem Services (FES) addressed and the specific characteristics of each area (i.e. size of the LL, type of land ownership, local context, etc.), the Living Labs adopted diverse organizational and management strategies, as well as tailored approaches to stakeholders' engagement. This section provides, for each LL, the following information and analysis:

- Description of the implemented participatory process, including the LL Coordinators' perspective (see Annexes 2 and 4);
- List of stakeholders involved and related analysis (see Annex 1);
- Stakeholders' map (see Annex 3);
- Stakeholders' power/interest matrix (see Annex 3).

3.2.1 Austria

Participatory process implemented and stakeholders' analysis

The **participatory process** and **stakeholder's involvement** in the Austrian LL were based on existing connections and network. The main source of contacts was the WoodCluster Network (33% of stakeholders) but also new contacts were involved from other provinces, f.e. Forstplanung Tirol.

Informal interactions with the stakeholders were carried out, even during different events, not directly organised for the Forest EcoValue project.

Political participation was limited due to competing priorities, low perceived urgency and insufficient initial alignment with regional policy agendas (e.g., biodiversity strategy, climate adaptation policies). Future LLs in Austria should explicitly integrate provincial policy actors early.

Both online and in person meetings were organised.

The main stakeholders were the Styrian Forest Owners Association and individual Forest Owners. The dialogue with policy makers and regional actors was held through workshops and events.

The Austrian LL illustrates the challenges of applying PES models in highly fragmented private-forest landscapes. Compared to other LLs, Austria shows strong association-based structures (Waldverband), but low initial engagement from political actors. This indicates that PES adoption depends not only on forest structure but also on institutional design and policy alignment.

The LL coordinating team had all the necessary **tools** to implement the process of participation.

The online meetings proved to be the best modality to reach more stakeholders, enabling them to easily access activities. In-person meetings were organised only with established stakeholders.

One of the core learnings in the LL was that building a relationship of trust was fundamental to meet the stakeholder needs and expectations. For this reason, dedicated sessions were organised to interact with the stakeholders, listen to them and explain the project more clearly.

During the participatory process, a new added value for the key stakeholders had to be invented, as the stakeholder list has changed.

The LL coordinating team has a **positive experience with the implemented process of participation**.

They believe it was a great opportunity to engage the stakeholders and show them that this initiative acknowledges and celebrates the forests owners who want to adopt new forest management strategies,

especially in the context climate change and increased risks of forest disturbances.

The LL had achieved although not large but a tangible impact as five small-scale Forest Owners were rewarded financially for biodiversity and carbon sequestration and storage measures, while at least a hundred of Forest Owners and other representatives of the forest and wood-based sectors were informed about the innovative opportunities for the FES payments and inspired for action.

In the Austrian LL the **total number of defined stakeholders** during the project was **36**.

The LL **included 11 target groups (92%)** of the 12 target groups defined for the project. Only target group 15 International organisation, EEIG was not represented.

Figure 11: Initial distribution of the categories of target groups identified for the stakeholders' list in the Austrian LL.

The category **Others (TG 15- 16)**, which includes Forest Owners, is the **principal one**, with 11 stakeholders, **followed by** the target groups 12-14 related to **Interest groups including NGOs**, with 6 presences. The **less represented** target group is the **Local public authority (TG 5)**, with only one occurrence.

At the end of the project the LL individuated **5 main stakeholders**, the **14% on the total of stakeholders listed** (they were 36 at the initial stage), which were mainly public authorities at a regional level, business support organisations and enterprises (also banks) and small-scale private Forest Owners.

The stakeholders' analysis highlighted a significant evolution in the engagement process in terms of the number of stakeholders involved and participating. For this reason, the situation at the end of the project in the case of the Austrian LL is also reported below.

Figure 12: Final distribution of the categories of target groups involved in the Austrian LL.

In general, in the Austrian LL, the number and target groups of stakeholders identified in the stakeholders' list and the number and type of invited and participating stakeholders in the process and in the events did not match, due to the dynamic nature of the living lab itself. The living lab is an innovative and experimental infrastructure, thus, by definition, it is subject to continuous evolution. This aspect was identified in the process of participation of the Austrian LL, as can be seen from the following paragraphs, where the data related to the events are presented.

The synthesis of the **organised meetings** and the main related data is presented below.

Table 3: Summary of key data relating to events held in the Austrian LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ¹	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2023/12/04	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Power point presentation	Agreement on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the set of FES: carbon stability, habitat maintenance business model: reverse auction
2024/01/29	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	9%	2	Power point presentation	The Styrian Forest Owners Association will be a partner in the LL implementation and reaching out the Forest Owners, also by providing a catalogue of possible measures to its members
2024/04/29	Open public event	FEV project partner	100%	2	Power point presentation	Raise awareness about the project and forest ecosystem services
2024/06/28	Open public event	External body - IRE AG	NA	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press release • Expert talk Information material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intercepted a mutual interest to participate in the project Organisation of another meeting
2024/08/22	Open public event	FEV project partner	5%	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentations • Satisfaction survey • Expert talk Report release 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon stability vs greenwashing • Measures to support carbon stability • Natural regeneration and climate resilience • Criteria for assessing sustainability established in advance • Avoiding price dumping and empowering Forest Owners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimising bureaucracy • Need of clear communication Engagement of different sectors: Forest Owners and industry

¹ The interception rate is given by the ratio between the number of stakeholders participating in the event and the number of stakeholders invited.

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ¹	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2024/12/06	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Power point presentation	Approval of the conditions for participation and the application
2025/02/17	Open public event - Intermediate event	FEV project partner with key stakeholder	100%	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentations • Press release (after the event) • Expert talk Video 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tested activities of the LL were welcomed by the Forest Owners' community • Opportunity to reach a greater number of Forest Owners, that confirmed the interest in the project <p>High interest in the future expansion of the concept by inclusion of more sustainable forest management practices in the portfolio</p>
2025/05/26	Open public event	FEV project partner	17%	1	Power point presentation	Forest Owners informed, questions answered
2025/10/08	Open public event - Final event	FEV project partner	14%	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation <p>Regional roadmap</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nine letters of commitment to support the Roadmap of the Living Lab were collected. • Comprehensive publicity measures were implemented. <p>A press release was issued to</p>

						share the Styrian activities and insights from the project with a broader public audience.
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The LL organised **9 events** during the project,

- 22% were meetings;
- 11% were workshops;
- 67% were public events.

Public events and in the online mode were the best working format for the LL.

The **intermediate and final events** were held during public open events.

During the process, **41 Forest Owners have directly participated in the LL**, while the total number of Forest Owners who either attended the first public event or the reflection workshop reached approximately 180.

The following table presents the **total number of stakeholders that were contacted and attended the events**, by target group, during the participatory process in the Austrian LL.

Table 4: Analysis of total stakeholders contacted and total stakeholders participating in events, aggregated by target groups in Austria

Target group	Stakeholders contacted	Stakeholders participating	Interception rate [%] ²
National public authority (TG 1 and 2)	20	-	0%
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4)	18	9	50%
Local public authority (TG 5)	15	1	7%
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7)	32	4	13%
SMEs (TG 8 and 9)	142	16	11%
Business support organization (TG 10)	36	5	14%
Sectorial agency (TG 11)	17	2	12%
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14)	25	7	28%
General public (TG 13)	270	65	24%
Higher education, research org. (TG 17)	17	7	41%
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 - 19)	11	1	9%
Others (TG 16)	385	174	45%
TOTAL	988	291	29%

The **interception rate of the stakeholders**, which represents the ratio between the stakeholders effectively attended the events and the stakeholders contacted, was around **29%**.

The Austrian LL showed higher engagement capacity for the following target groups: Regional public Authority (TG 3-4), Others (TG 16) and Higher education, research organisations (TG 17).

Considering the number of contacts, the target group Others (TG 16), namely Forest Owners, had a high participation, with 45% of participating among those contacted. The unusually high number of contacts reflects the fragmented ownership structure in Austria and underscores systemic limitations in reaching small private forest owners without embedding outreach through established institutions (Forest Owner

Association, Chamber of Agriculture, district forest authorities). Future participation strategies should formalise these institutional channels. Lastly, the Regional public authority (TG 1-2) had the 50% of participation, considering the number of stakeholders contacted for this category.

National public authority (TG 1 and 2) did not participate, even if specifically invited to the final event.

At the same time, the target group 18-19 International organisation, EEIG, which was not in the stakeholders list, was involved with one representative.

At the end of the process of participation, it was found that **all the target groups were invited** to some events, even if only 11 were identified in the stakeholders list.

The distribution of stakeholders participating in the events, divided by target groups, is represented in the following Figure.

Distribution by target group of stakeholders participating in events - LL AUSTRIA

Figure 13: Distribution by target group of stakeholders participating in events in the Austrian LL.

The target group **Others (TG 16)**, which also represents forest owners, was the most **actively involved** in terms of total number, in the organised events (around 60% of the participants), followed by the General public (TG 13).

Stakeholders mapping - Stakeholders power/interest matrix Austrian LL

Following, the stakeholders' power/interest matrix and the stakeholders' map for the Austrian LL are presented.

The Austrian LL defined two matrices and two maps, applying them to the main FES of the living LL.

Stakeholders' power/interest matrix - Carbon storage and sequestration (Bundled with timber provision and habitat maintenance)

Figure 14: Stakeholders' power/interest matrix related to the FES Carbon storage and sequestration (bundled with timber provision and habitat maintenance) of the Austrian LL.

Stakeholders' power/interest matrix – Habitat maintenance

Figure 15: Stakeholders' power/interest matrix related to the FES Habitat maintenance, of the Austrian LL.

Stakeholders' map - Carbon storage and sequestration (Bundled with timber provision and habitat maintenance)

Figure 16: Stakeholders' map related to the FES Carbon storage and sequestration (bundled with timber provision and habitat maintenance) of the Austrian LL.

Stakeholders' map - Habitat maintenance

Figure 17: Stakeholders' map related to the FES Habitat maintenance of the Austrian LL.

According to the stakeholder maps and matrices, the **key stakeholders** (subjects with high power and high interest) in the Austrian LL were linked to those identified target groups (TG) listed in the matrix legend: the **forest owners**, representing private entities (TG 15 and 16) and **a public actor, the Styrian Forest Owners Association** (TG 3 and 4). These were also the only two entities capable of obstructing the process (veto players) in both the FES considered.

Then, going to the **primary stakeholder level**, the two maps related to the FES considered two other subjects (both single entities in this case and not groups): the Raiffeisen Regional Bank of Styria (private entity - TG 15 and 16) and the Regional Forestry Directorate (public entity - TG 3 and 4). Thus, it results that key and primary stakeholders were composed by the Forest Owners (a group of subjects), two public entities (The Styrian Forest Owner Association and The Regional Forestry Directorate) and a private entity (The Raiffeisen Regional Bank), covering 4 Target Groups (TG 3 and 4 and 15 and 16).

Enlarging the maps, it outcomes that there was a wide group of **secondary stakeholders**, which were more diverse in composition and cover all target groups. It is therefore clear that collaboration between regional public entities, private entities (forest owners), and entities capable of financing projects (in this case Raiffeisen Regional Bank) was central to the guarantee the process started in this LL.

The fact that different types of secondary stakeholders were involved in the process and the presence of a various and high number of interactions between them and the key stakeholders means that the LL was linked to the local contest receiving inputs and contamination from private, public and associative sectors. A lot of people and interest groups (stakeholders) have been involved and contacted during the process, testifying an active participation process inclusive of all the local instances and creating an open dialogue especially with the forest owners.

In terms of tensions, it can be noted that they all related to secondary stakeholders and therefore did not affect key and primary stakeholders. Two of the three tensions reported involved NGOs, while there was only one communication breakdowns/ tensions between one NGO and one public body involved on the FES Habit Maintenance (in this case it is supposed due to the high sensibility of the ONG, the WWF on this subject, that was the core activity of the association).

Finally, it can be noted a weak link with research and training institutions concerning the FES Carbon Storage and sequestration (TG 17) and support associations (TG 10), which could be strengthened to assist and promote the participatory process.

3.2.2 France

Participatory process implemented and stakeholders' analysis

The French LL covered two different areas, which were nevertheless considered jointly, in all the analysis and deliverables.

The **participatory processes carried out in the two areas constituted a single overall process** rather than two separate paths.

The **process of participation** implemented in the French LL was largely based on one-to-one meetings. The French LL already includes forestry operators, who were in contact with stakeholders. Contacts with stakeholders took place through individual interviews and individual meetings.

Intermediate group events were also organised, but mostly individual meetings took place.

The LL had the necessary **tools** for implementing the process of participation, but it was difficult. The difficulty was getting back in touch with the various stakeholders. Sometimes they didn't want to be contacted again, and they were reluctant to do more interviews because they just wanted the results.

The LL has a **general positive experience** with the participatory process implemented, but their direct involvement as stakeholders themselves made the process more difficult, even for the pre-existing relationships with all the parties involved.

In the French LL, the **total number of identified stakeholders** during the project was **20**.

The LL **included 9 target groups** of 12 (**75%**) in the definition of the specific stakeholders to be involved in the process.

The excluded target groups from the list were: Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7), General public (TG 13) and Others (TG 16).

Figure 18: Distribution of the categories of target groups identified for the stakeholders' list in the French LL.

The category **Business support organisation (TG 10)**, is the **principal one**, with 5 stakeholders, **followed by** the target group 5 related to **Local public authority**, with 4 presences.

In general, in the French LL, only the number of stakeholders identified in the stakeholders' list and the number of invited and participating stakeholders in the process and in the events did not exactly match, due to the dynamic nature of the living lab itself. The living lab is an innovative and experimental infrastructure; thus, by definition, it is subject to continuous evolution. This aspect was identified in the

process of participation of the French LL, even if less pronounced than in other LLs, because, as instance, the target groups identified, then were almost the same invited to the events. The detailed data are presented in the following paragraphs. The synthesis of the **organised meetings** and the main related data is presented below.

Table 5: Summary of key data relating to events held in the French LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ³	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2024/05/22	Workshop only upon invitation – Intermediate event	FEV project partner	86%	4	Expert talk. Field presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific functioning of the Moise watershed as a pilot site for sharing good forest practices for preserving water quality in other living labs (type of exploitation, period of exploitation, etc.). • The market model of water protection service was also very appreciated by representatives as a way to pay foresters for protecting water. The legal scheme proposed in this specific framework could be reproduced in another territory
2024/09/25	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	100%	4	Power point presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of important stakeholders and contacts • Preparing for the next local meeting to promote the project and reach the goals in the Living Lab • Specific context and results in the Savoy Department in terms of methodology and initiatives Build on what already exists for sharing good forest practices for preserving forest ecosystem services
2025/01/13	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Power point presentation	Overall interest, but followed by no action
2025/01/16	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	100%	3	Power point presentation, Signed list of participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approach developed by the project: 1) using the « fresco » as a tool to raise awareness and train ONF technical staff in Auvergne Rhone Alpes 2) relying on the Living Lab approach to spread technical and financial solutions that can be replicated across other territories Market model of using the tourist tax to promote and maintain recreational FES was identified as an interesting solution in attractive territories

Table 5: Summary of key data relating to events held in the French LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ³	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2025/01/28	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Phone call	Update on activities, approved by Thonon Agglomeration, but waiting for the responsible person in the forest field
2025/02/10	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	2	Power point presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Association with Jens A as a senior researcher and adviser for the project • Identification of important stakeholders and contacts Preparing for the next local meeting to promote the project and reach the goals in the Living Lab
2025/02/14	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Phone call	Update on activities, interest by Thonon Agglomeration, but still waiting for the responsible person in the forest field
2025/02/17	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	3	Power point presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Association with Dephine B as commissioner of Alpine space for ANCT • Identification of important stakeholders and contacts Preparing for the next local meeting in order to promote the project and reach the goals in the Living Lab
2025/06/11	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	96%	6	Power point presentation, Expert talk Signed list of participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approach developed by the project: 1) using an animation tool (Fresco, FES workshop) as a tool to raise awareness among technicians (ONF, CNPF, etc.) but also among elected officials and the general public 2) relying on the Living Lab approach to spread technical and financial solutions that can be replicated across other territories While Living Lab experiences were illustrated and appreciated by the partners, discussions revealed that there was a lack of a clear and established framework to guide the promotion of FES

2025/09/29	Workshop only upon invitation – Final event	FEV project partner	84%	8	Power point presentation, Expert talk Satisfaction survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing financial and technical ways to be prioritised among local and global stakeholders • Using the fresco as a tool to raise awareness of forest ecosystem services and disseminate information about the project
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The LL organised **10 events** during the project,

- 50% were meetings, which include some phone calls;
- 50% were workshops, the only one corresponds with the intermediate event;
- 0% were public events.

Both meetings and workshops were the best modality to reach the stakeholders.

The **intermediate and final events** were held during workshops.

The following table presents the **total number of stakeholders that were contacted and attended the events**, by target group, during the participatory process in the French LL.

Table 6: Analysis of total stakeholders contacted and total stakeholders participating in events, aggregated by target groups in France

Target group	Stakeholders contacted	Stakeholders participating	Interception rate [%] ⁴
National public authority (TG 1 and 2)	2	1	50%
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4)	6	6	100%
Local public authority (TG 5)	21	20	95%
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7)	-	-	-
SMEs (TG 8 and 9)	4	3	75%
Business support organization (TG 10)	9	8	89%
Sectorial agency (TG 11)	24	22	92%
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14)	9	9	100%
General public (TG 13)	-	-	-
Higher education, research org. (TG 17)	8	7	88%
International organization, EEIG (TG 18-19)	1	1	100%
Others (TG 16)	1	1	100%
TOTAL	85	78	92%

The **interception rate of the stakeholders**, which represents the ratio between the stakeholders effectively attended the events and the stakeholders contacted was around **92%**. In general, there was a high capacity of involvement of the stakeholders (the interception rate was never lower than the 50%), simplified by the already existent network.

10 target groups were contacted and involved in the meetings. Only one target group which was excluded in the stakeholders' list, then was involved in the active process of participation: Others (TG 16), through the participation of a representative of private foresters in the department.

In total, the LL stated that around **50 private Forest Owners** were involved in the process of participation through presentations, specific meetings, or other contacts. They were probably reached

through the representative of private foresters in the department.

The distribution of stakeholders participating in the events, divided by target groups, is represented in the following Figure.

Figure 19: Distribution by target group of the stakeholders participating in events in the French LL.

The target groups, **Sectoral agency** (TG 11) and **Local public authorities** (TG 5), were the most **actively involved**. Instead, the Business support organisation (TG 10), which was the most numerous in the list, did not reach a high percentage of involvement in the active process. The **least involved** target groups were **National public authority** (TG 1-2), **International organisation, EEIG** (TG 18-19), and **Others** (TG 16), each with only one participation.

Stakeholders mapping - Stakeholders power/interest matrix French LL

Following, the stakeholders' power/interest matrix and the stakeholders' map for the French LL are presented.

Stakeholders' power/interest matrix

Stakeholders' map

Figure 21: Stakeholders' map of the French LL.

The map and matrix of French LL highlights how the key actors were all public entities at various levels, national and regional (ONF, CNPF, and DRAAF - TG 1 and 2), local (Grand Annecy in Thonon Agglo - TG 5), plus INRAE, which was also a public research body. This peculiarity of the French LL is linked to the involvement of the public owners of forests, as **key actors**, so the national public bodies played a more central role in the process because they are directly concerned also as owner and non-only as regulators, together with the local public bodies (Municipalities, etc.). This is due to a high fragmentation of the Private Forest owners that often have small part of the forest not allowing to be powerful in the area.

In terms of points of interest, it is worth noting the kind of links between the AURA Region and the ONF (Office National des Forêts) and between the CNPF and the two local authorities that were also key actors (Grand Annecy and Thonon Agglo) due to different priorities between bodies that have the Forest sector as primary focus and bodies involved on other services and activities that considered forests not as the first area of interest. Broadening the circle to include the primary actors, other public entities were added, such as the Tourist Office and the two main municipalities (which were also the entities that could have veto or therefore hinder the project if not actively involved), while private entities and associations were secondary actors as were the Department of Haute-Savoie (74) and the Wood Cluster, which was a weak link with the CNPF, the public entity of reference for the sector.

3.2.3 Germany

Participatory process implemented and stakeholders' analysis

The German LL covered two different areas, which were nevertheless considered jointly, in all the analysis and deliverables.

The **participatory processes carried out in the two areas constituted a single overall process** rather than two separate paths.

The LL had a direct connection with the stakeholders, which were mainly represented by two Forest Owners, strongly involved in the **participatory process**. The LL also reached some forest associations. The LL Coordinator contacted the stakeholders by e-mail and mainly by phone calls, in addition to the mandatory workshops and events.

Involving local communities, the Bavarian state forestry department and the forestry authority proved difficult during the participatory process. The main reasons were a lack of time and human resources. Contact with local decision-makers was therefore postponed until the project had concrete results and solutions to offer.

The LL not only had online-meetings or exchanges via phone calls with the stakeholders, but they also organised workshops and on-site visits.

The LL informed about their activities through different channels, for example via the German project partners' LinkedIn channel and the "latest news" rubric on the project partners' homepage, and a newsletter that was established during the Living Lab to especially reach political regional and national target groups.

The LL had all the necessary **tools** to implement the process of participation.

The LL has a **not completely positive experience on the process of participation** carried out, because the Forest Owners were very involved, but at the same time a wider participation from different target

groups would have been desirable.

The **stakeholders' list** changed during the process because at the beginning it was more extensive and different in terms of targets. During the process some new targets were reached like: expert on the business area and some policy makers.

In the German LL the **total number of defined stakeholders** during the project was **79**.

The LL **included 10 target groups** of 12 (**83%**) in the definition of the specific stakeholders to involve in the process.

The target group not included in the list were Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7) and Sectorial agency (TG 11).

Figure 22: Distribution of the categories of target groups identified for the stakeholders' list in the German LL.

The category **Local public authority (TG 5)** was the **principal one**, with 36 stakeholders, **followed by** the target groups 12-14 related to **Interest groups including NGOs**, with 13 presences. The **less represented** target groups were Business support organisations (TG 10), General public (TG 13) and SMEs (TG 8 and 9). The target group Others (TG 15-16), which includes Forest Owners, represented the 6% of the total stakeholders of the LL.

At the end of the project the LL individuated **27 main stakeholders**, the **34 % on the total**, which were mainly interest groups included NGOs and Others (Private Forest Owners and the Archdiocese Munich-

Freising).

In general, in the German LL, the number and target groups of stakeholders identified in the stakeholders' list and the number and type of invited and participating stakeholders in the process and in the events did not match, due to the dynamic nature of the living lab itself. The living lab is an innovative and experimental infrastructure, thus, by definition, it is subject to continuous evolution. This aspect was identified in the process of participation of the German LL, as can be seen from the following paragraphs, where the data related to the events are presented.

The synthesis of the **organised meetings** and the main related data is presented below.

Table 7: Summary of key data relating to events held in the German LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ⁵	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2024/05/16	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	No materials, phone call	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing contact with private forest owners in the WBV who meet the criteria for Living Lab • Inquiry to municipalities regarding interest in participating in the project
2024/06/10	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Information material from e-mail	Egling municipality could not be involved in the project
2024/07/02	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Information material	Assess for the participations by the responsible forestry manager
2024/07/25	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	100%	2	Power point presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of forestry data for biophysical assessment • Preparation of forest data • Preparation of indicator factsheets • Research for further business ideas and models which match the interests of the FO • Establishing contacts with other stakeholders
2024/10/17	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Power point presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of forestry data • Scheduling of second introductory presentation in front of the management and forestry personnel
2024/12/09	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	Power point presentation	Feedback to ifuplan on the participation in the project FEV in timely manner

2025/01/13	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	No material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ifuplan will carry out a biophysical assessment of the selected areas • ifuplan will carry out in-depth research on the 4
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⁵ The interception rate is given by the ratio between the number of stakeholders participating in the event and the number of stakeholders contacted.

Table 7: Summary of key data relating to events held in the German LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ⁵	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
						business ideas: burial forest, healing and spa forest, product line weak wood - green chemistry, drinking water supply <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There will be an on-site appointment with the people involved
2025/01/16	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	No materials	Insight into Klosterwald GmbH and receipt of a lot of information about burial forests
2025/02/25	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Technical documents with indicators and data • Good practices factsheets • Tablet with 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtaining various information about permit required and whether the burial forest is still forest • Transmission of contacts for the development of various business ideas • Review and further development of the indicator calculation for the ecosystem services

					geodata of calculated indicators	
2025/03/24	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	100%	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation with a summary of good practices • Technical documents with indicators and data • Tablet with geodata of calculated indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defined Ecosystem services of interest, good practices and business ideas of interest • organisation of field trip • development a suitable business concept based on the stakeholders' interests • Definition of data recovery • Research contents for FNR funding • Explore the possibilities of data transfer of biophysical assessment (indicator data for FES)

Table 7: Summary of key data relating to events held in the German LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ⁵	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2025/09/26	Open public event - Intermediate event	FEV project partner	1%	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Speech of private forest owner 	It is necessary to adequately reward forest ecosystem services financially. In order to motivate even sceptical Forest Owners to change their forest management practices, attractive financial incentives must be created.
2025/09/30	Open public event - Final event	University of Freiburg (National Forest Conference 2025)	NA	NA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Poster presentation on the FEV project and the living lab process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Over 600 conference participants • About 50 presentations and 20 posters sessions • Stakeholders from the following target groups participating: TG 1&2, TG 3&4, TG 5, TG 11, TG 16, and TG 17

The LL organised **12 events** during the project:

- 80% were meetings
- 10% were workshops
- 10% were public events

Online meetings and phone calls were the best solution for the LL.

The **intermediate and final events** were held during public open events.

In detail, **two Forest Owners** were continuously involved in the process. One was the private forest owner L.B. and the other forest owner participating in the process was the ecclesiastical organization “Archdiocese Munich-Freising”.

The following table presents the **total number of stakeholders that were contacted and attended the events**, by target group, during the participatory process in the German LL.

Table 8: Analysis of total stakeholders contacted and total stakeholders participating in events, aggregated by target groups in Germany

Target group	Stakeholders contacted	Stakeholders participating	Interception rate [%] ⁶
National public authority (TG 1 and 2)	4	1	25%
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4)	3	-	-
Local public authority (TG 5)	1	1	100%
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7)	1	-	-
SMEs (TG 8 and 9)	1	1	100%
Business support organization (TG 10)	-	-	-
Sectorial agency (TG 11)	4	-	-
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14)	15	2	13%
General public (TG 13)	-	-	-
Higher education, research org. (TG 17)	4	-	-
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 - 19)	-	-	-
Others (TG 16)	2316	34	1%
TOTAL	2.349	39	2%

The **interception rate of the stakeholders**, which represents the ratio between the stakeholders effectively attended the events and the stakeholders contacted was around **2%**. This low result is especially linked with the very high number of stakeholders contacted in the category of Others (TG 16), which shifted the order of magnitude in respect of the size of the other groups involved.

The category of Local public authority (TG 5), which was the most numerous in the list of defined stakeholders, was the less involved with only one stakeholder contacted, while the target group Others (TG 16) was the most contacted.

Other target groups mentioned as stakeholders then were not included in the events organised like: International organisation, EEIG (TG18-19), Business support organisation (TG 10) and General public. On the other side, some target groups did not respond at all to the call for the events like Regional public authority, Enterprise, except SMEs, Sectorial agency and Higher education and research.

The distribution of stakeholders participating in the events, divided by target groups, is represented in the following Figure.

Figure 23: Distribution by target group of the stakeholder participating in events in the German LL.

The target group **Others (TG 16)** was the one most **actively involved** in terms of total number, in the organised events (more than 89% of the participants), while the other category had only one representative.

Stakeholders mapping - Stakeholders power/interest matrix German LL

Following, the stakeholders' power/interest matrix and the stakeholders' map for the German LL are presented.

Stakeholders' power/interest matrix

Figure 24: Stakeholders' power/interest matrix of the German LL.

Stakeholders' map

Figure 25: Stakeholders' map of the German LL.

The stakeholders' map and matrix for LL in Germany show that the key stakeholders were **two large private forest owners**, one of whom had veto power, i.e., the power to block the project (the forest owner

L.B. TG 15 - 16). Other primary actors included the two municipalities where the forests are located (TG 5) and an interest group (TG 12-14).

The matrix shows that most of the entities involved, even at the secondary level, were linked to the public sector, while the private sector and civil society are underrepresented, perhaps due to the concentration on only two private landowners on which the LL is located. In terms of relationships, there was a weak link between the key actors and the primary stakeholders, offset by alliances between the key actors and different interest groups.

In terms of the type of targets involved, there were also international actors among the target groups (TG 18-19), which were not present in other LLs.

3.2.4 Italy

Participatory process implemented and stakeholders' analysis

To implement the participatory process, a database of stakeholders was created and organised according to the target groups defined in the project. The list did not undergo significant changes during the project, as it proved to be extensive and complete from the very beginning.

The Italian LL used several communication channels to reach out to stakeholders and broaden their involvement, including emails, phone calls and in-person contacts. The LL Coordinator organised a number of meetings, some broad and inclusive, others smaller and more focused, sometimes involving single key stakeholders.

At the initial stage, the participatory process was designed to allow stakeholders to discuss challenges and opportunities related to the project topics. During the implementation phase, however, the LL Coordinator took the lead in developing the proposal for solutions, as stakeholders lacked the specific technical skills needed to contribute to the detailed work. Stakeholders were therefore involved step-by-step, mainly to validate the progressive hypotheses and the proposals developed.

The main tools used in the participatory process were PowerPoint presentations, as the audience was mostly composed of non-young participants.

The Italian LL is overall satisfied about the process of participation and acknowledges that the pilot action could have been further strengthened by allocating additional time and budget for actually testing the business model.

In the Italian LL the **total number of identified stakeholders** during the project was **155**.

The LL **included 9 target groups** of 12 (**75%**) in the definition of the specific stakeholders to involve in the process.

The target group not included in the list were National public authority (TG 1 and 2), General public (TG 13) and international organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19), while the category OTHERS, without target group indication, was included, but most likely referred to target 16.

The list also includes stakeholders for whom no target group was specified (7% of the total).

Figure 26: Distribution of the categories of target groups identified for the stakeholders' list in the Italian LL.

The category **Local public authority (TG 5)** was the **principal one**, with 41 stakeholders, **followed by** the target groups 8-9 related to **SMEs**, with 37 presences and Interest groups including NGOs (TG)12-14, with 31 occurrences. The **less represented** target groups were Higher education and research (TG 17) and Sectorial agency (TG 11), with only one representative.

In the Italian LL, the total number of identified Forest Owners was 45, with an incidence of 29% on the total of stakeholders listed.

In general, in the Italian LL, the number and target groups of stakeholders identified in the stakeholders' list and the number and type of invited and participating stakeholders in the process and in the events did not match, due to the dynamic nature of the living lab itself. The living lab is an innovative and experimental infrastructure, thus, by definition, it is subject to continuous evolution. This aspect was identified in the process of participation of the Italian LL, as can be seen from the following paragraphs, where the data related to the events are presented.

The synthesis of the **organised meetings** and the main related data is presented below.

Table 9: Summary of key data relating to events held in the Italian LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ⁷	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2023/07/11	Meeting	FEV project partner	86%	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the use of material coming from the management of public and private green areas could be interesting, but there are doubts about the economic feasibility because there are obviously additional processes. • instead of paying for the material, the user company could pay for the sustainable management intervention, whose positive impacts could be valorised for marketing and the social balance sheet • Possibility for the company to support investments in expenses for the purchase of machinery to be made available to the network of local companies • Provision of municipal spaces for the construction of the plant. • The use of chestnut bark for the production of the material could be a very interesting hypothesis: it currently represents a problem because it cannot be used in other processes • interesting use of chestnut leaves as an alternative to burning, which is currently a large source of particulate emissions • An aspect to be explored further is the use of waste heat from district heating to dry biomass.

2024/05/15	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	4	Informal call	Use in GEOMAG processes: - Forest biomass: higher price than expected but positive impacts on ecosystem services - by-products from nuts and chestnuts
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Table 9: Summary of key data relating to events held in the Italian LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ⁷	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2024/05/22	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	37%	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation 	<p>Identification of the main points of interest that should be addressed</p> <p>Identification of some good practices already being carried out in the area</p> <p>New hints for potential business models</p> <p>Further expansion of the stakeholder database</p>
2024/07/16	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	10%	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Satisfaction survey 	<p>Identification of the main points of interest that should be addressed</p> <p>Identification of some good practices already being carried out in the area</p> <p>New hints for potential business models</p> <p>Further expansion of the stakeholder database</p>
2024/12/05	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation 	There were no agreement, result, or goal reached though the discussion.
2025/09/05	Open public event - Intermediate event	FEV project partner	11%	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Signed list of participants • Satisfaction survey 	Collection of letters of interest and general approval of local roadmap.
2025/11/27	Open public event - Final event	FEV project partner	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	The event had a broader public outreach purpose, going widely beyond the Living Lab area. Therefore, it is not relevant for assessing the Italian LL participatory process, and its attendance data are not included in

						this analysis.
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The LL organised **6 events** during the project,

- 50% were meetings;
- 33% were workshops;
- 17% were public events.

Meetings were the best solution for the LL to implement the process.

The intermediate event was held during a public open event in the LL area and was aimed at validating the proposed business models and solutions. It also served to present and share with local stakeholders the results developed within the project.

The final event represented the closing milestone of the Italian Living Lab process and aimed to disseminate its results more widely, sharing the outcomes achieved and positioning them within the broader framework of the FEV transnational pilot action.

This event took place with a slight delay (27th November 2025) compared to the initial schedule, as it was originally planned for October.

The decision to postpone was motivated by the strategic sequencing of the Living Lab’s final phase. In particular, **the intermediate event, held in Ormea on the 5th September 2025**, was expressly dedicated to a moment of restitution towards local stakeholders of the Living Lab, aimed at presenting the feasibility assessment and the business model and validating and formally approving the Regional Roadmap developed through the participatory process.

Shortly afterwards, **the second Capacity Building Workshop, conducted online on the 25th September 2025**, reached a much broader audience, mainly composed of practitioners — including professionals, researchers, and public authorities from several Italian Regions. It was designed as a capacity-building and knowledge-sharing event, comparing the solutions emerging from the Italian Living Lab with those developed in other contexts, and stimulating a structured reflection on replicability, scalability, and integration into policy frameworks.

Given the close timing of these two initiatives and their complementary objectives and audiences, the Living Lab Coordinator considered it more effective to schedule the final event at a slightly later stage, thus allowing sufficient time to prepare and promote it properly. This approach also helps maintain the attention and interest of audiences over time, ensuring that the final event can reach a relevant number of participants and achieve greater visibility and impact in disseminating the results of the FEV pilot action.

During the process, **7 Forest Owners have directly participated in the LL.**

The following table presents the **total number of stakeholders that were contacted and attended the events**, by target group, during the participatory process in the Italian LL.

Table 10: Analysis of total stakeholders contacted and total stakeholders participating in events, aggregated by target groups in Italy

Target group	Stakeholders contacted	Stakeholders participating	Interception rate [%] ⁸
National public authority (TG 1 and 2)	-	-	-
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4)	6	3	50%
Local public authority (TG 5)	100	12	12%
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7)	5	2	40%

Business support organization (TG 10)	12	3	25%
Sectorial agency (TG 11)	2	1	50%
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14)	19	9	47%
General public (TG 13)	9	1	11%
SMEs (TG 8 and 9)	66	13	20%
Higher education, research org. (TG 17)	11	6	55%
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 - 19)	-	-	-
Others (TG 16)	4	2	50%
TOTAL	234	52	22%

The **interception rate of the stakeholders**, considering the ratio between the stakeholders contacted for the events and the stakeholders effectively participating was around **22%**.

The category of High education, research org. (TG 17), achieved the best results in terms of contacts and consequent involvement.

The Local public authority (TG 5), although the most numerous group and with an increased number of contacts compared to the initial list, showed a relatively low engagement rate – similar to Target Groups 8 and 9 (SMEs), which also recorded limited participation despite many being contacted.

The General public (TG 13), initially excluded in the stakeholders list, was later involved, though only within the framework of the intermediate public event, which reached a broader audience.

The distribution of stakeholders participating in the events, divided by target groups, is represented in the following Figure.

Distribution by target group of stakeholders participating in events - LL ITALY

Figure 27: Distribution by target group of the stakeholder participating in events in the Italian LL.

The target groups **SMEs (TG 8-9)** and **Local public authority (TG 5)** were the one most **actively involved** in terms of total number, in the organised events (respectively 26% and 24% of the participants). Instead, the target group of Sectorial agencies (TG 11) did not participate.

Stakeholders mapping - Stakeholders power/interest matrix Italian LL

Following, the stakeholders’ power/interest matrix and the stakeholders’ map for the Italian LL are presented.

Stakeholders’ power/interest matrix

Figure 28: Stakeholders’ power/interest matrix of the Italian LL.

Stakeholders' map

Figure 29: Stakeholders' map of the Italian LL.

As regards the Italian LL there were a very high number of stakeholders on the list (155), 29 of which had high power and high interest. Among these, the private sector predominated with companies (TG 6 and 7 + TG 8 and 9), followed by trade associations and business support associations (TG 10). However, there were also public sector entities at both the local (municipalities TG 5) and regional (TG 3 and 4) levels, that were relevant also as veto Player⁹ (i.e. Regione Piemonte, Municipalities of Ceva, Garessio and Ormea). Also, the Maritime Alps Park could be a veto Player for the woods, included in the respect and protected areas.

There was a significant number of entities with little power but a high level of interest in the project (109 entities), reflecting the active participation of the entire territory involved in the process.

All relevant productive sectors (agriculture, industry, cooperation) were represented within the Living Lab. Their role is particularly relevant given that individual forest owners were not directly involved, mainly due to high land properties fragmentation and the presence of a Forest Consortium and three Landowner Associations (“Associazioni Fondiarie”), which acted as intermediaries representing private owners. This situation highlighted the challenge posed by the fragmented ownership structure in the area which can be overcome precisely thanks to the existence and involvement of the owner groups involved like Landowners Association, Forest Consortiums and trade associations.

3.2.5 Slovenia

Participatory process implemented and stakeholders' analysis

The Slovenian LL for implementing the **process of participation** paid attention to contact the forest unit, to reach the Forest Owners, through e-mail and, in some cases, directly by phone call. The main channel to contact and to maintain the communication was by e-mail.

The LL established contacts with some Forest Owners represented by lawyers (so they need to be very prepared about the matter), which was a great opportunity for the activities of the LL. Unfortunately, it was not possible to put them in contact with the municipalities.

Personal contact with the stakeholders was fundamental, so the LL attended specific conferences. The goal of the LL is broader than the project perimeter, so it worked in different direction.

The LL informed about their activities through different channels: local newspapers, municipality channels, Slovenia Forests Service, Facebook, regional newspapers, newspapers.

The LL attended different conferences about specific topics related to the project (forests and torrents), to reach more key stakeholders and to achieve a direct contact.

The pilot actions plans were not stressed as topics: the LL stressed the environmental services topic, as biomass, they presented good practices, confront different opinions and collect the needs of the territory, as the necessity to reduce conflicts in the future.

The workshops were useful, because they reached different stakeholders. They also organised an educational course about torrent management.

The LL had most of the needed **tools**, but it missed to exchange knowledge with partners, it would like to see how the other LLs worked on the participatory process. For the Slovenian LL, it would be good to know how was in different countries.

⁹ A veto player is an individual or collective actor whose agreement is necessary to change the status quo in a policy-making process. They have the power to block or "veto" new policies or reforms.

The Slovenian LL is overall **satisfied about the process** of participation, but it would like to cooperate more in the water sector.

In the Slovenian LL the **total number of defined stakeholders** during the project was **58**.

The LL **included 8 target groups** of 12 (**66%**) in the definition of the specific stakeholders to involve in the process.

The target groups not included in the list were Sectoral agency (TG 11), General public (TG 13), Others (16), even if Forest Owners were involved, and International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19).

In the list also presented stakeholders without target group indications (14% of the total).

Figure 30: Distribution of the categories of target groups identified for the stakeholders' list in the Slovenian LL.

The category **Interest groups including NGOs (TG 5)** was the **principal one**, with 12 stakeholders, **followed by** the target groups 6-7 related to **Enterprises, except SMEs** and **National public authority (TG 1 and 2)**, both with 9 presences. The **less represented** target group was the Business support organisation (TG 10), with only one representative.

In general, in the Slovenian LL, the number and target groups of stakeholders identified in the stakeholders' list and the number and type of invited and participating stakeholders in the process and in the events did not match, due to the dynamic nature of the living lab itself. The living lab is an innovative

and experimental infrastructure, thus, by definition, it is subject to continuous evolution. This aspect was identified in the process of participation of the Slovenian LL, as can be seen from the following paragraphs, where the data related to the events are presented.

The synthesis of the **organised meetings** and the main related data is presented below.

Table 11: Summary of key data relating to events held in the Slovenian LL

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ¹⁰	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
2024/04/05	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Expert talk • Signed list of participants 	The cooperation continues
2024/05/15	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Signed list of participants 	Presentation of the project and future cooperation
2024/07/06	Meeting	FEV project partner	100%	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Expert talk • Signed list of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cooperation continues • Exchange of information and technical data • Crucial to have regular communication with key stakeholders
2024/11/26	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner co-organised with external actors	100%	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Expert talk • Signed list of participants • Press release • Field excursion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beginning of the cooperation in torrent management system • Inclusion of organizations with strong field and expert knowledge about torrents • Plan to involve other sectors in second WS
2024/12/17	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	100%	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert talk • Maps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local forests support is crucial to implemented ideas • Local forests have a lot of knowledge

2025/04/01-03	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner co-organised	100%	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Expert talk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good responses to the workshop reported • Achieved new knowledge about torrent supervision
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¹⁰ The interception rate is given by the ratio between the number of stakeholders participating in the event and the number of stakeholders contacted.

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	INTERCEPTION RATE [%] ¹⁰	KEY STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	MATERIALS AND TOOLS	MAIN RESULTS
		with external actors			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press release • Field excursion • Signed list of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation between different institutions and countries • Cooperation between stakeholders working in the field of forestry and torrents
2025/04/14	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	100%	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Expert talk • Signed list of participants • Satisfaction survey • Press release • Field excursion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement of the stakeholders on many issues • Suggestions for improvement were heard from the municipal administration • Participants had the opportunity to hear other points of view
2025/03/06	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	10%	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Signed list of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality saw that biomass can be used efficiently, that there is a lot of potential for it in the municipality • Capacity building among different stakeholders • No single forest owner came to the event, despite the interest

2025/05/06	Workshop only upon invitation	FEV project partner	100%	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Expert talk • Signed list of participants 	There were some good proposals, ideas, useful for future work
2025/05/28	Open public event - Intermediate event	FEV project partner	14%	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power point presentation • Expert talk • Signed list of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information to the public about the project • Not high attendance • Welcoming approach during the debate allowed the expression of both worries and proposals
2025/11/25	Workshop only upon invitation - Final event	FEV project partner	21%	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roundtables with moderators • Expert talk • Signed list of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future steps were planned in the field of all three ESS • Participants showed interest for collaboration in the future

The LL organised **11 events** during the project,

- 27% were meetings;
- 64% were workshops;
- 9% were public events.

Workshops were the best modality for the LL to implement the process.

The **intermediate event** was an open public event. The **final event** was held during a workshop.

A total of **37 Forest Owners** were involved in the Slovenian LL. Specifically, 129 questionnaires on biomass use were distributed, and responses were received from 37 Forest Owners. Unfortunately, the Forest Owners' involvement was limited to this phase and it did not develop in an active presence during the events carried out by the LL.

The following table presents the **total number of stakeholders that were contacted and attended the events**, by target group, during the participatory process in the Slovenian LL.

Table 12: Analysis of total stakeholders contacted and total stakeholders participating in events, aggregated by target groups in Slovenia

Target group	Stakeholders contacted	Stakeholders participating	Interception rate [%] ¹¹
National public authority (TG 1 and 2)	63	31	49%
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4)	4	3	75%
Local public authority (TG 5)	36	12	33%
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7)	17	5	29%
SMEs (TG 8 and 9)	4	3	75%
Business support organization (TG 10)	9	1	11%
Sectorial agency (TG 11)	3	1	33%
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14)	20	9	45%
General public (TG 13)	-	-	-
Higher education, research org. (TG 17)	11	7	64%
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 - 19)	1	-	0%
Others (TG 16)	108	6	6%
TOTAL	276	78	28%

The **interception rate of the stakeholders**, which represents the ratio between the stakeholders effectively attended the events and the stakeholders contacted, was around **28%**.

Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4) and **SMEs** (TG 8 and 9) reached the highest interception rate (both around the 75%), followed by **Higher education, research org.** (TG 17). The other target groups

achieved interception rates of less than 50%.

Moreover, **some of the target groups which were not included in the stakeholders' list were contacted and took active part in the events**, like Sectoral agency (TG 11), Others (TG 15-16). International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19), which were not included in the list, were then invited, but did not attend. In total, **11 target groups (92%) were invited to the events**. In the group Others, Forest Owners are included, and it was the most numerous groups contacted, even if the less reached in participation.

The distribution of stakeholders participating in the events, divided by target groups, is represented in the following Figure.

Figure 31: Distribution by target group of the stakeholder participating in events in the Slovenian LL.

The target group **National public authority (TG 1-2)** was the one most **actively involved** in terms of total number, in the organised events (around the 39% of the participants), followed by the **Local public authority (TG 5)** -around the 15% of the participants-. Instead, the target group of Sectoral agency (TG 11) and Business support organisation (TG 10) were the less participant (both lower than the 2% of the total participants).

Stakeholders mapping - Stakeholders power/interest matrix

Following, the stakeholders' power/interest matrix and the stakeholders' map for the Slovenian LL are

presented.

The Slovenian LL defined three matrices and maps, applying them to the main FES of the living LL.

Stakeholders’ power/interest matrix – Torrent management

Figure 32: Stakeholders’ power/interest matrix related to the FES Torrent management of the Slovenian LL.

Stakeholders' map – Torrent management

Figure 33: Stakeholders' map related to the FES Torrent management of the Slovenian LL.

For this FES (Torrent management), there were no stakeholders with high interest and high power and all the subjects in the first two areas (Key Stakeholders) were public national entities; likewise, there were no subjects with veto power. Unfortunately, however, there was a conflict between two key actors (MNRSP and MAFF), perhaps due to overlapping competences between the agencies, and between the Water Agency and the Slovenia Forest Service (SFS). Conflicts between key stakeholders and primary actors were considered important in the management of the LL, just as the suboptimal communication between the municipalities involved and the SFS highlights a point of attention in the relationship between the national agency and local authorities.

The majority of stakeholders involved were from the public sector, while civil society was represented only by a generic group (General Public) that was positioned as a secondary stakeholder.

The high level of interest shown by secondary stakeholders referring to the target group (TG 17) linked to research and education was positive, as it was the existence of a consolidated link between these entities and the SFS.

Stakeholders’ power/interest matrix – Biomass

Figure 34: Stakeholders’ power/interest matrix related to the FES Biomass of the Slovenian LL.

Stakeholders' map – Biomass

Figure 35: Stakeholders' map related to the FES Biomass of the Slovenian LL.

With regard to the FES biomass, it should be noted that the key players were the SFS and the municipality concerned (which also had veto power on the issue), but cooperation was missed between them. The primary actors were Forest Owners (TG 15 and 16) and companies (TG 6 and 7) that work with biomass, but unfortunately there was also a lack of good communication between them.

Companies working with biomass also had difficulties in communication with the municipality. Similarly, communication between individual Forest Owners and their trade association (secondary actor) was not

positive, instead there was a good channel of exchange with the SFS. There were few stakeholders involved and there was no involvement of civil society and the public sector, apart from the above-mentioned stakeholders (municipality and SFS).

Stakeholders’ power/interest matrix – Tourism/Recreation

Figure 36: Stakeholders’ power/interest matrix related to the FES Tourism/Recreation of the Slovenian LL.

Stakeholders' map – Tourism/Recreation

Figure 37: Stakeholders' map related to the FES Tourism/Recreation of the Slovenian LL.

For this FES (Tourism and Recreation), the main actor (Key actor) was the municipality (TG 3 and 4) and there were no actors with veto power. On this front, two other public entities at the national level (SFS and Institute of the Republic of Slovenia for Forest Conservation – TG 1 and 2) also had a high level of interest and medium power and were primary actors together with forest owners (TG 17). Unfortunately, there was a weak communication channel between these two public entities at the national level, while the SFS had a functional communication channel with forest owners. The two entities had not open communication channels with the municipality, which could be a problem given the municipality's key role in this sector.

Unlike the two previous FES, some civil society and private sector associations were involved in tourism as secondary actors, which is a sign that other entities may become involved in the development of tourism services, both at the association and small business levels. These entities currently had open, albeit weak, channels of communication with the Municipality.

The three FES in Slovenian LL involved different stakeholders. Tourism was certainly the one with the widest margin for involvement of external parties, which played a secondary role, while biomass had a limited number of stakeholders, but these correspond to the supply chain, from forest owners to companies working with biomass, with the municipality as the controlling entity, from supply to the final product. Thus, barring any obstacles posed by the public (see the municipality's power of veto), it could easily be developed in the LL area.

Water management, on the other hand, involved many public entities at various levels and research institutions, so the matrix would need to be rebalanced with greater involvement from the private sector and the local area in terms of local stakeholders.

3.3 Report of the stakeholders' satisfaction survey

A satisfaction survey was submitted to the stakeholders of the LLs in September 2025, when all the meetings were completed, and the final event was approaching.

The results are presented below. The English version of the survey is provided in the annexes (see Annex 5).

3.3.1 Austria

Number of obtained replies: 3

All the three interviewees represented the category of Public and private Forest Owners in LL territories (Others, TG 15-16).

All interviewees heard about the Forest EcoValue project and LL through the following channels:

- Online event 'Forest Monday' organised by the Styrian Forest Owners' Association, in early 2025;
- Waldverband Aktuell, January 2025 issue (magazine of the Styrian Forest Owners Association).

On average, all of them attended a single event/meeting organised by LL and intend to attend future events. The topics covered during the events/meetings were considered quite interesting by all. Among the topics covered, the following were particularly relevant:

- everything related to the forest of the future;
- the funding programme for small Forest Owners;
- the combination of ecological and economic activities.

Opinions on participation in the project are quite diverse, ranging from "not very involved", because greater involvement was not necessary as a private forest owner, to "very involved".

No particular changes were reported with regard to initial participation, as the various stakeholders always felt involved (some even though they only participated once).

Everyone gained new knowledge by participating in the various events/meetings and everyone considers the approach and solutions proposed by this project to be valid. The activities carried out by the project can have a positive impact on the territory.

None of the stakeholders believe they can play a role in the future by contributing to the implementation of the business models discussed in the pilot action.

Suggestions: the online application forms for the project were not very intuitive.

3.3.2 France

Number of obtained replies: 7

The seven respondents represented the following categories:

- Public or private forest owners in LL's territories (Others TG 14-15);
- Local public authority (TG 5);
- National public authority (TG 1-2);
- Regional public authority (TG 3-4).

All respondents heard about the Forest EcoValue project and the LL through the following channels:

- ONF;
- As part of ONF-COFOR technical meetings on payments for environmental services, in 2023;
- CNPF;
- INRAE in 2021;

- Alpine Space Programme.

Three stakeholders participated in two events/meetings organised by LL.

Three stakeholders participated in six events/meetings organised by LL. One stakeholder participated in a single event/meeting organised by LL.

All respondents intend to participate in upcoming events that will be organised.

The topics covered during the events/meetings were found to be very interesting by all the respondents. Among the topics covered, the following are of relevance:

- enhancement and promotion of forests services;
- research into an economic assessment of environmental services applied to public forests;
- partnerships;
- interest in and enhancement of aspects related to the multifunctionality of forests.

Opinions on participation in the project are all positive, with respondents feeling very involved in the process.

Contrasting opinions were reported regarding initial participation: some stakeholders felt involved throughout, some said they felt more involved in the initial phase of the project, while others, on the contrary, felt more involved during the final phase of the project. The reasons given are as follows:

- Change of position/territory;
- Late involvement in the project;
- Programme paving the way for many future ideas and projects;
- Involvement of the Forchat Local Health Authority and the future Planbois Local Health Authority, for which the question arises of how to promote services.

They all acquired new knowledge by participating in the various events/meetings. The knowledge acquired covers the following topics:

- Regional innovations;
- New issues related to forestry.

All respondents believe that the approach and solutions proposed by this project are valid. The activities carried out by the project can have a positive impact on the territory. Below are the suggestions of the various respondents:

- timber is no longer profitable; beneficiaries of forests services must contribute to forest financing;
- future solutions for forest conservation and improvement must be developed;
- uncertainties in the forestry sector and dependence on the timber market may limit options in this area; an assessment of the environmental services provided by forests, prior to a voluntary payment mechanism, represents a promising prospect; considering the contribution of forests to human societies beyond timber production alone would allow for better policy integration of forest issues and stimulate the investments needed to ensure the sustainability of resources and services;
- adapting solutions to the specific context of each territory;
- need to finance mountain forests beyond timber sales; need to engage elected officials on multifunctionality and the value of different uses.

All stakeholders believe they can play a role in the future by contributing to the implementation of the business models discussed in the pilot action:

- operating on a small scale and in a politically coherent manner (urban area), with a significant proportion of public forests and assumed multifunctionality, this project provides a set of measurement tools to promote PES mechanisms and a different way of considering forests;
- in the Greater Chambéry and Greater Lac areas;
- in Ardèche, where forests are generally unproductive but where issues related to water, protection, tourism and leisure are important, such an approach makes it possible to overcome a view of forests as “risky” or “invasive”;
- Involvement of the CNPF to raise awareness of issues among institutional representatives.

3.3.3 Germany

Number of obtained replies: 1

The respondent represented the Holzkirchen Forest Owners' Association (Others, TG 15-16). This organisation was not aware of the Forest Ecovalue project and LL through the media.

It participated in only one event/meeting organised by LL and intends to participate in future events.

The topics covered during the events/meetings were considered quite interesting. Among the topics covered, the following was of relevance: the monetary valuation of various forest ecosystem services.

The opinion on participation in the project was positive, with the Association acting as an intermediary between Ifuplan and Forest Owners.

There have been no changes since the initial participation, with the Association always feeling involved during the various phases of the project.

Participation in the meetings allowed for the acquisition of new knowledge, but no details were provided in this regard.

The approach and solutions proposed by this project are considered very valid, and the Association believes that the activities carried out could have a positive impact on the territory if and when the results of the project are made known at the political level, both at the federal level and in the EU.

The Association believes it can play an important role in the future by contributing to the implementation of the business models discussed in the pilot project, particularly in private forests. Together with state-owned agricultural and forestry companies, they are the first point of contact for private Forest Owners for all forest-related issues.

Suggestions: It should be noted that the Association's contact with Ifuplan has been very pleasant and positive.

3.3.4 Italy

Number of obtained replies: 8

The respondents represented the following categories: local public authorities; businesses; interest groups; Forest Owners; regional public authorities; others (freelancers and consultants); Education (high school's head)

Not all respondents had heard about the Forest Ecovalue project through the media; only some of them had heard about it through the following channels:

- Mailing list
- Facebook
- Municipality of Ormea

- Local newspapers

On average, all respondents had participated in several events/meetings organised by the LL and intended to participate in future events.

The topics covered during the events/meetings were considered very interesting by all. Among the topics covered, the following were of relevance:

- payment for ecosystem services;
- biodiversity enhancement;
- mushrooms; management of abandoned forests;
- carbon credits;
- economic development and possible market implications.

Opinions on participation in the project tend to be similar, with everyone feeling involved throughout the project; only one respondent said they felt involved in the initial phase but then distanced themselves in the next phase.

Everyone gained new knowledge by participating in the various events/meetings, including:

- carbon credits - forest management;
- new supply chains.

Almost all respondents considered the project's approach and proposed solutions to be valid, with only one respondent expressing limited confidence in their validity and providing no further justification.

All stakeholders believe that the activities carried out by the project can have a positive impact on the area. The following considerations/arguments were highlighted:

- local economy and forest management
- landcare and enhancement of the forest system
- activation of synergies between the various actors in the area

Some stakeholders believe they can play a role in the future by contributing to the implementation of the business models discussed in the pilot action:

- through the management of services aimed at improving biodiversity
- through training and communication programmes in the

area Suggestions: no suggestions were highlighted.

3.3.5 Slovenia

Number of obtained replies: 3

The respondents represented the following categories:

- national public authority (TG 1 and 2)
- local public authority (TG 5)
- others (TG 16).

All three had heard about the Forest Ecovalue project and the LL through the following channels:

- Tržič Municipality website
- Facebook page
- Tržič Living Lab through the local newsletter
- Workshop at the Tržič business incubator

On average, everyone attended three events/meetings organised by the LL and intend to attend future events.

The topics covered during the events/meetings were considered very interesting by everyone.

Among the topics covered, the following were considered particularly relevant:

- watercourse management,
- sustainable mobility,
- recreational activities in forests,
- tourism,
- protection of forests from excessive harvesting of mushrooms and wild fruits and from motor vehicle noise,
- safety in forests,
- interconnection with all people who carry out activities and work in forests
- more educational/informative activities for forest visitors.

Opinions on participation in the project are rather mixed: some feel more involved in the initial phase of the project, others only in the phase already underway.

Everyone gained new knowledge by participating in the various events/meetings: lots of new and interesting information about waterways and biomass. An analysis was presented on how landowners think about and perceive recreational activities and tourism in forests.

There are conflicting opinions on the validity of the approach and solutions proposed by this project. All stakeholders believe that the activities carried out by the project can have a positive impact on the area. The following considerations are highlighted:

- the opinions wish and expectations of the various stakeholders (landowners, environmentalists, hikers, mountain bikers, municipalities, entrepreneurs, etc.) are so far apart that it will be difficult to reach an agreement. Much more work and communication will be needed, especially in the area of awareness raising.
- considering that this project was one of the rare occasions when all those involved in forestry activities/work were invited and participated, and that communication between the various stakeholders began to establish itself well, this is the first, biggest and most important step towards any future improvement.
- Some stakeholders believe they can play an important role in the future by contributing to the implementation of the business models discussed in the pilot action:
 - informing people/Forest Owners about the results of the project.
- the municipality could act as a mediator between the various stakeholders and try to reach a consensus on the areas and extent of recreational development in the forests.

Suggestions: It is suggested that some parts of the forests be closed to the public and accessible only to permit holders. Permit holders should be local residents and those who carry out forestry work/activities, inhabitants of the municipality of Tržič, who love this area.

3.4 Media presence in the Living Labs

3.4.1 Austria

For the Austrian LL there is n. 3 press release provided in 3 moments:

- 7th November 2024;
- 12th of March 2025;
- 22nd of October 2025.

3.4.2 France

For the French LL there are n. 3 press releases provided in 3 moments:

- 21st of October 2023;
- 22nd of May 2024;
- 4th of September 2025 (to promote the event of the 29th of September).

3.4.3 Germany

The media presence in the German LL is following summarised:

- N. 2 thematic newsletter sent by IFUPLAN to its mailing list, in October 2024 and in September 2025;
- N. 2 news published on Sonntag Plus web site, both in November 2024;
- N. 1 press release sent the 31st of October 2024 with 7 publications on the media in the following days.

3.4.4 Italy

For the Italian LL the press review includes the following articles in local and Regional media:

- 17-20th of May 2024, 8 articles;
- 24th of October 2024, 3 articles (after the meeting in Ormea and the press Release of Finpiemonte);
- 10th September 2025, 2 articles.

3.4.5 Slovenia

For the Slovenian LL the press review includes scientific articles and publications in local and Regional Websites, social network and media:

- N. 2 scientific publications (in 2024 and in 2025)
- N. 2 articles in local newspaper (both in 2025)
- N. 4 news in Blog or social networks (Facebook in this case), one in 2023 and three in 2025.

3.5 Results of the participatory process in the single Living Labs

This section reflects the experiences of the LL Coordinators on the participatory process. In the annexes, the interview form and the complete interview notes are included.

3.5.1 Austria

The LL network and activities were not restricted to the municipality but defined by the borders of the province of Styria. The choice of such boundaries was informed by the interest and motivation of the main stakeholder, Styrian Forest Owners Association, as well as the chosen payment mechanism – reverse auction – which required a higher number of participants. The Austrian LL tested the first reverse-auction mechanism for biodiversity and carbon-storage-stability measures in the Alpine region. This represents a replicable low-cost mechanism for small-scale forest owners and fills a gap in Austria's

current PES landscape. This allowed the participation of the stakeholders from the entire province; thus, the LL could welcome a wider network, establish new connections and have a greater impact.

One of the last events was a huge success because the LL organised a session to answer to stakeholders' questions and to reach their necessities and, thanks to this approach, the LL had a lot of applications to participate in the business model pilot, with some Forest Owners getting funding to implement biodiversity and carbon storage measures, which meant to have a concrete impact on the territory. Building a relationship of trust was fundamental.

The LL also published informational and promotional materials in specialised magazines.

The main issue was to reach the principal stakeholders' target, represented by the Forest Owners, because of the type of network of the LL, based mainly on university, associations at a regional level and wood cluster. At the same time, the LL registered a resistance in participation from Forest Owners and even from political actors, when they did not understand the process and the project, it was necessary to reach their trust at first, and not always it was easy.

For these reasons and even for the large number of tasks to carry out in the project, the in-person meetings did not work. The stakeholders were involved in many activities and organising to be present offline was challenging.

In parallel, the LL experienced to work always with the same stakeholders, who, at the end, were frustrated to hear the same contents and consequently lost interest and reduced participation.

The LL think that a wider access to the network of the main stakeholders' targets is necessary and that the key stakeholders, like Forest Owners, had to be partner of the project.

More economic resources would be appreciated and even more time to find the stakeholders that really want to be active part of the process would be needed.

3.5.2 France

The main success of the participatory process was that FES always manage to attract the stakeholders' attention. FES are an attractive topic.

The French LL got a response in terms of availability and involvement by the stakeholders. This represents one of the successes.

Other successes were the joint designing of certain actions. The participatory processes showed to be more efficient when there was a window of opportunity. For example, The LL had two living laboratories. One of the two laboratories had the opportunity to talk about forests, trees and similar topic. This made the process more fluid and attractive.

When the LL started, it wasn't clear to the coordination team how to implement the participatory process. This aspect was not related to guidelines, because there were resources available about that aspect. The LL had difficulties in focusing the main objective of the process of participation. The main issue was the organisation of it. Between the experimentation phase and the methodological phase, it was difficult for the LL's team to understand how the two phases worked and how to get started.

The LL didn't enter the participatory process with a clear understanding from the outset.

One of the main difficulties, but at the same time an opportunity, was that the French LL was itself one of the stakeholders, with pre-existing relationships with all the parties involved. This aspect did not halt the process, but it should be considered in further guidelines.

One of the outcomes was the necessity to draw up specific guidelines for the parties involved, so all the partners can work in a clearer and simpler way.

3.5.3 Germany

A major strength was the active engagement of forest owners, who showed a strong commitment to driving change, exploring innovative business opportunities linked to forest ecosystem services, and contributing meaningfully to co-creation activities. Over time, a dedicated core group of forest owners emerged as key actors in advancing the process.

Despite this positive momentum, several factors constrained wider stakeholders' integration and impact. Engagement of public authorities, forestry institutions, and key decision-makers remained limited due to restricted financial and human resources, competing priorities, and low availability for participation. Stakeholders' recruitment required significantly more time than anticipated. Initial efforts prioritised the development of concrete solutions and business models prior to initiating dialogue with municipalities and other institutional actors, resulting in temporary stagnation of the process.

In summary, while the Living Lab successfully mobilised committed forest owners and generated valuable insights, the experience highlighted the need for earlier institutional engagement, broader outreach strategies, and dedicated resources to strengthen continuity, legitimacy, and impact in future participatory processes.

3.5.4 Italy

The principal results in the Italian LL were the proactive and collaborative spirit of the main stakeholders, the positive welcome to the proposed ideas and the constructive observations given.

The LL did not notice any specific criticality in the implementation of the participatory process.

One of the main challenges for the Italian LL was to introduce and discuss complex topics with stakeholders who did not have the technical knowledge to address such a complex issue.

A possible way to further strengthen the participatory process would be to align the Living Lab's technical activities around a more specific focus (e.g. a narrower selection of ecosystem services), using it as an opportunity to take further steps in developing and implementing the solutions proposed by the project.

This approach could build on the validation work already achieved, while enhancing practical experimentation and learning-by-doing, although it would require additional time and resources.

3.5.5 Slovenia

The LL proposed valuable contents for the workshops. The main result was that the LL proposed something useful, interesting and concrete for the territory.

There was a good attendance, if not considering Forest Owners participation.

Majors participated to a lot of workshops, thus the municipalities were well involved.

The Slovenian LL needed a lot of time for organising workshops about specific and high-level topics.

Final event in September was forced for their participatory process status. For the process, it would be better to have fewer events, but better organised.

The communication with high political channels was difficult. The LL could not show all the topics and information to the high levels because they were not actually part of the participatory process.

One of the main issues was that Forest Owners did not attend the activities. The LL carried out different approaches and channels for communicating, informing and involving them in the events. The LL also conducted a survey and the response had been positive, but at the end, at the activities, the Forest Owners did not participate.

A major exchange, sharing of the modalities of involvement and update about the process in the different LLs would be useful.

The coordination team concluded that more time and financial resources would have been necessary for field trips and to create a network of contacts.

A soft approach in stakeholders' involvement was quite useful, to directly know the people, quality of connection was important and even personal contact was fundamental.

4. PART 2 – Transnational analysis of the participatory process in the network of Living Labs

4.1 Participatory process implemented and stakeholders' analysis

The **pilot action** within the FEV project was structured into four sub-phases, planned to span a total of 18 months of activities in each of the five target areas.

- 1) Preparation phase;
- 2) Planning phase;
- 3) Implementation phase;
- 4) Evaluation phase.

The next paragraph evaluates how the participatory activities were implemented across the five LLs, in terms of organisation, timing, and overall consistency with the initial plan.

For each phase, the following paragraphs **highlight (in blue)** the activities directly related to the participatory process, together with the corresponding results and outputs, which confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach. The remaining activities, not highlighted in blue, refer instead to more technical aspects connected to the project's content and not directly to the participatory process.

1 - **Preparation Phase** (expected duration of 3 months)

It included the following activities:

- Mapping of actors to be involved;
- Territorial analysis, including the collection of relevant experiences, knowledge of existing markets, preliminary data, and framework policy analysis;
- Definition and agreement on the **Participatory Process methodology**;
- Establishment of **first** contacts.

The **output** of this phase was the **preliminary stakeholders' list**, and the consequent **preliminary power/interest matrix** and, where possible, the stakeholders' **map** for each Living Lab (Tool D2).

In each LL, a preliminary stakeholders' list was established and subsequently revised and expanded throughout the process, resulting in a more comprehensive final version that confirms the effectiveness of the participatory methodology.

During the initial phase, the main challenge was to clearly define the role of each stakeholder. Consequently, the first versions of the stakeholder matrix evolved in all LLs into a final one by the end of the process, reflecting the results of ongoing interactions and engagement activities. At this initial stage, the stakeholder map was considered a working hypothesis to be validated throughout the process. For this reason, the present analysis focuses on the final version, in which the actual interactions among stakeholders were verified.

Concerning the participation process methodology, the multilateral meetings with all LL Coordinators highlighted the differences among the areas and their different capacities to develop the participatory process. During this preparation phase, the collective meetings offered an opportunity for all LL Coordinators to exchange thoughts and ideas on the approach to be used, to clarify doubts, and to learn

from each other's, thereby improving the overall effectiveness of stakeholder engagement and networking.

In some cases, the preparation phase required more than 3 months, the first contacts, the answer of the people involved and to the seasonality (i.e. in summer is more difficult in some areas to find people in activity).

2 – **Planning Phase** (expected duration of 6 months)

It included the following activities:

- **Start of the participatory process;**
- Public event to launch the LL;
- Local meetings including the presentation of examples and good practices, co-planning sessions, collection of feedback, discussion of possible solutions, identification of key market players, and analysis of markets and business models.

The planning phase marked the start of the participatory process and the official opening of the LLs.

According to the initial plan, an official launch was foreseen and was indeed carried out, although in different forms across the areas.

In some LLs, a more informal approach proved more effective, with one-to-one meetings aimed at explaining the project and engaging key stakeholders during the early stages. Consequently, in certain cases, the LL launch was not a public event but rather took place through press releases and private meetings.

Local meetings were organised in all LLs, though with different formats, depending on stakeholders' availability, their role and level of relevance (key, primary, or secondary) and the methodology adopted. The main outputs of this phase consists of the **meeting minutes** produced within each LL.

3 – **Implementation phase** (expected duration of 6 months)

It included the following activities:

- Verification of the developed market hypotheses, with respect to the economic context;
- **Transnational exchange and comparison;**
- Identification of the policy need and decision makers;
- Definition of an action plan for local actors;
- Capacity building workshops.

In this advanced phase, the participatory process activities became more technical and closely connected to the thematic work of the LLs, also addressing the specific features of the selected forest ecosystem service markets and related business models.

The pilot action was ongoing and continuously supported through regular monthly alignment meetings among the LL Coordinators, with a specific focus on the participatory process. The aim was to share results, achievements and challenges encountered during this operational stage at the international level, promoting continuous exchange, comparison between local cases, and one-to-one support where needed.

The main outputs included the interviews with the LL's coordinators and the minutes or registration files of both the transnational meetings and the local meetings held within each LL as part of their process.

4 – **Evaluation phase** (expected duration of 2 months)

It included the following activities:

- Closing the pilot action;
- **Reflection on the outcomes of the participatory process and on future perspectives;**
- **Final public event in LLs to present the results;**
- Risen awareness of political decision makers at different level;
- Access to transnational capacity building opportunities (online Winter School).

The evaluation phase included a final public presentation, supported by press releases and media coverage in each LL, as well as the collection of the stakeholders' feedback through a satisfaction survey.

These events served primarily as restitution moments, addressed not only to those who had participated – even marginally – but also to individuals or organisations that had heard about the LL during the previous months and were interested in learning about the outcomes of the pilot action.

Considering the previous phase, it was observed that a two-months period may be a too short to conclude the participatory process, as the timing of the final event also depends on local circumstances and on the availability of the involved stakeholders to participate. Furthermore, since the final event is public, its promotion and preparatory activities can require more time than initially planned.

In fact, three Living Labs managed to stay on schedule and held their final event in October 2025, while two Living Labs (Italy and Slovenia) organised theirs at the end of November 2025.

It should also be noted that, in the case of the Italian Living Lab, the intermediate event held on 5 September was conceived as the Living Lab's closing event and it was aimed at validating the proposed business models and solutions. It also served to present and share with local stakeholders the results developed within the pilot action. The final event of 27th November, instead, had a broader public dissemination scope and was therefore not relevant for the evaluation of the participatory process of the Italian LL (for this reason, participation data from that event are not included in this analysis).

In Slovenia, the final event took place on 25th November with a slight delay and represented a key step in the Living Lab. For this reason, the present deliverable waited for the results of the Slovenian final event in order to include them and finalise a consolidated version of this analysis.

In conclusion, the organisation into phases was respected across all LLs, and the adoption of a similar structure helped the LL Coordinators to effectively follow and implement each steps of the process.

At the end of the participatory process, the following recommendations for replication emerged:

- The timing of each phase should remain flexible, allowing LL Coordinators an additional 2–3 months to complete individual phases and to adapt the focus according to stakeholder responsiveness taking into account that the total process will need the same time to be completed and that the internal division of the phases depends on the local situation (i.e. in some case the LL Coordinator may need more time to identify the stakeholders or to organize meetings).

- The **launch of the LLs** should be adapted to local contexts and the level of engagement of key stakeholders. In some cases, **bilateral meetings** proved more effective than public launch events for involving the main actors.
- The evaluation phase requires more than 2 months, as it involves collecting stakeholders' feedback (e.g. through surveys) and engaging the participation of a wider audience.
- More generally, the participatory process implemented by the different LLs in the FEV project was managed largely autonomously within each area, reflecting the diversity of territorial context and the different needs for connecting and involving stakeholders.

In total, **348 stakeholders were identified and mapped in the FEV pilot action**. The distribution of total stakeholders identified by each LL is represented below.

Figure 38: Distribution of stakeholders divided by LL in the different counties identified in the project.

In terms of **quantity**, the highest number of stakeholders identified was in the **Italian LL**, with **155 stakeholders**, while the lowest was in the **French Living LL**, with **20 stakeholders**.

Table 13: Analysis of total stakeholders identified and listed in the LLs and in the FEV project

LL's country	Number of identified stakeholders
Austria	36
France	20
Germany	79
Italy	155
Slovenia	58
Total number of identified stakeholders	348

If we analyse the **type of stakeholders** based on the **target groups (TG)** set in the project, it results that **Local public authorities** (TG 3 and 4) and **Interests groups including NGOs** (TG 12 and 14) were the

most relevant and engaged categories, together with SMEs (TG 8 and 9). Instead, Others (TG 15-16) and General public (TG 13), were less represented.

Figure 39: Total distribution of stakeholders listed in the whole project, divided by target group.

Considering the meetings implemented in the LLs, in some cases, the **invitations to the events were extended to a wider audience**, as some LLs contacted additional stakeholders beyond those initially identified in their lists. As a result, the level of active participation was sometimes broader than expected.

Table 14: Analysis of total stakeholders invited and participating in the LLs and in the FEV pilot action

LL's country	Total number of stakeholders contacted	Total number of stakeholders participating
Austria	988	291
France	85	78
Germany	2.349	39
Italy	234	52
Slovenia	276	78
TOTAL	3.932	538

Analysing the data related to the organised meetings and events, it was registered **a total interception rate of around 14% for the whole pilot action**. Overall, **538 stakeholders participated in the events**.

Below, **the interception rate of each LL** is represented. The percentage refers to the ratio between the total number of stakeholders participating in the events of the single LL in relation to the total number of stakeholders contacted/invited by each LL in that specific event.

Figure 40: Total interception rate of stakeholders during the events organised in each LL in the whole project.

The analysis shows that in the LLs **where the number of stakeholders initially identified was lower**, such as in France, the **involvement rate was higher**. This can be explained by the fact that a smaller number of stakeholders allows for deeper and more frequent interactions, consequently resulting in easier engagement. In contrast, the other LLs achieved active involvement from less than half of the contacted stakeholders. In the specific case of Germany, the number of stakeholders' invitations was particularly large (about two orders of magnitude greater than the initial list), which naturally led to a lower interception rate. However, if considering the active participation related only to the 79 stakeholders initially included in the list, the rate reached 48%. Similarly, in Slovenia, the percentage of participation related to the initial stakeholders' list reached 95% active presence.

Analysing the **target groups involved in the events of the pilot action** (see the Figure below), it is evident that the LLs Coordinators primarily aimed to engage **Forest Owners** (Others TG 16), who were the most frequently contacted and also among the most actively participating stakeholders (41,7% of the total participants).

The General public (TG 13), mainly reached through the organisation of public events, also represented an important category, although they represented less than 13% of the total participants.

SMEs (TG 8 and 9) and Local public authority (TG 3 and 4) were also key target groups for the LLs, but the participation was lower than expected, their actual participation was lower than expected, with percentages of less than 7% and 8%, respectively, among the total participants.

International organisation, EEIG (TG 18-19) was not a primary target group for the LLs; in fact, only the Austrian LL invited a representative from this category.

Figure 41: Total number of stakeholders involved in the project, divided by target groups and distinguished between those contacted and those who actually participated.

This **discrepancy** between the lists of identified stakeholders and stakeholders effectively invited and participating in the events can, in some cases, be attributed to the type and focus of the events organised, as well as to the evolution of the participatory process itself throughout the project.

During the FEV project, **48 events were held:**

- 43,8% were meetings (21 meetings);
- 29,2% were workshops only upon invitation (14 workshops);
- 8,3% were open public events (4 public events);
- 10,4% were intermediate events, one for each LL (5 intermediate events);
- 8,3% were final events, which occurred only in 4 LLs (4 final events).

Figure 42: Total number of events held during the whole project, divided by type.

80% of the **intermediate events** were organised as public events, only in France the intermediate event coincided with a workshop.

Examining the different timing of the implementation of intermediate events, which in some cases took place at the beginning of the process (e.g. in France), and in others towards the end (e.g. in Slovenia), it appears that the purpose of this type of event was not always clearly defined. It should also be noted, again, that the methods for implementing the participatory process were not always uniform across the various LLs.

60% of the **final events** were organised as public events, only in France and Slovenia the final event coincided with a workshop.

4 LLs held the final event and 1 was planned at the end of November 2025 (in Italy). In Italy, the final event of 27th November had a broader public dissemination scope and was therefore not relevant for the evaluation of the participatory process of the Italian LL and consequently for the whole Participatory Process.

Table 15: Analysis of total events held in the LLs and in the FEV project, by type

Type of event	Austria	France	Germany	Italy	Slovenia
N. meetings	2	5	8	3	3
N. workshops only upon invitation	1	5	2	2	6
N. open public events	6	-	2	1	2
N. total events	9	10	12	6	11

The preferred type of event was different for each LL. This reflects the different approaches and categories of stakeholders involved in the LLs of the project.

France did not organise open public events, whereas in Austria, it resulted in being the most effective way to foster interaction. In Germany, meetings were considered the most suitable format, while in Slovenia, workshops worked best. Italy organised fewer events overall, and no specific preferred format was substantially identified.

4.2 Stakeholders' maps and matrices analysis

The stakeholder maps and matrices created by the five LLs show how the participatory processes differed according to each specific LLs, the country context and its administrative organization. This is particularly evident in the maps where the key stakeholders vary significantly from one LL to another.

Furthermore, the map shows the variety of stakeholder involvement, which was broad across all LLs (almost all target groups have in fact been identified and involved in the process). However, some target groups, such as international entities or the general public, were sometimes included in the list but only marginally involved.

The matrices show that in all LLs, actors with both high interest and high power (the key stakeholders) were successfully identified. This represents a crucial prerequisite for assessing the potential to develop initiatives related to the identified Ecosystem Services.

The maps also indicate a limited number of conflicts in the territories and a few weaknesses of the communication channels between the stakeholders, sometimes even between relevant public bodies or different types of bodies like Public Administration at different level (e.g., local, regional, and state bodies).

Below, in synthesis, are the factors that emerge from the analysis of the five stakeholders' maps and matrices for the participatory processes:

- It is important to identify the type of Forest Ownership (from totally public to almost totally private), because Forest Owners are almost always key stakeholders.
- Local authorities and public bodies play a central role in general and in some cases have veto power¹², while in other cases they are also the owners of the land on which the LLs are located.
- The number of key and primary stakeholders is not high, so the LLs can focus on a small number of actors with whom to build a dialogue, even one-on-one, and then broaden the audience to secondary actors at a later, more public stage.
- It is important, within the participatory process, to consider the quality of relationships and the proper functioning of communication channels among the parties involved, as well as the possible presence of conflicts — for instance, with civil society — even at the level of secondary stakeholders. Such a situation was observed in only one of the processes examined.

4.3 Media presence in the project

The participatory process was implemented differently in each context, adapting to the specific territorial characteristics and the identified stakeholders, none of whom belonged to the media sector.

Regarding media coverage, concentrated on key moments, such as the launch of the Living Labs, transnational partners' meetings, and the intermediate and final events in LLs, for which the LL Coordinators prepared press releases and shared them with local and regional media.

Overall, the participatory process relied primarily on direct invitations and personal contacts. Media engagement was therefore considered useful only for promoting public events and disseminating the results of the participatory process to the wider local community.

4.4 Final remarks and lessons learned

Monitoring and supporting the participatory process of the LLs, together with the continuous comparison of experiences at transnational level, made it possible to identify both success factors and critical issues, as well as obstacles and enabling conditions that may facilitate the replicability of the process in other contexts and projects. These are summarised below:

- The process was supported by tools co-developed with the LL Coordinators, building on templates proposed by ERICA (minutes, surveys, and stakeholder lists) and by Finpiemonte/PP1 and Ifuplan/PP6, as WP2 leaders (stakeholder maps and matrices), and then tailored to the specific context of each Living Lab.
- The proposed format for the participatory process was tailored to each LL and its national context, based on the findings of the preliminary analysis phase and on the stakeholders list.
- The start of the contact activity with the territory was not easy because each LL had to choose most appropriate tools and formats (type of meetings and contacts) to initiate the process. For instance, the initial launch event planned at the preliminary phase was not always organised, and it was often preferred to start with direct, one-to-one contacts with potential key stakeholders.
- The lists of stakeholders, as well as the related maps and matrices, were continuously updated throughout the participatory process, with significant changes in numbers and roles over time; therefore, it was considered more appropriate to treat only those received at the end of the process as definitive. The fact that the number of stakeholders identified and contacted increased during the process was a positive result.
- Stakeholder engagement requires strong local coordination and communication skills; involving dedicated expertise in event management and external relations within LL local teams could have supported this work. Since the LL coordination teams were mainly composed of technical experts – a key requirement for the pilot action – these competences were less represented, which sometimes made the initial phase less smooth and, later, added some challenges in promoting the final event and ensuring broader media visibility at the local and regional level. Building a team with the right mix of technical skills and facilitation/communication skills is certainly a very complex challenge.
- The exchange of best practices, successful experiences and critical issues among LLs across different countries enabled ongoing interaction between coordinators, facilitating the sharing of challenges and the approaches adopted to address them. During the process, specific exchange sessions were organised, as well as individual support activities to further promote the sharing of good practices and help overcome challenges.
- The different approaches adopted in the management of the LLs and transnational interaction helped address local challenges and fostered the creation of a cohesive group of coordinators, aware of the process and the difficulties and opportunities in other LLs. However, the LLs Coordinators also indicated that additional opportunities for exchange would have been beneficial.
- Direct interviews with LL Coordinators were essential to complete the overview and description of each participatory process, since in some cases the analysis of data alone (stakeholders' lists, matrices and maps, minutes of the meetings) did not fully capture the relational aspects,

successes and challenges faced. This enabled a more in-depth discussion of the data analysis related to the participation process helped link the results of data processing with additional observations, thereby refining the overall understanding of the process.

- The submission of the satisfaction survey to the stakeholders was particularly challenging for the LLs. A low number of answers was collected, due to the difficulty to keep high their attention and interest about the participatory process improvement. The stakeholders were more interested in giving their feedback on the contents of the project rather than in the modality of involvement and participation.
- In terms of media presence, it should be noted that the absence of press officers in the LLs coordination team produced very heterogeneous material, ranging from scientific articles to posts on websites and social media. Presence in the local media is not continuous, but only sporadic and linked to major events.
- Regarding the division of the participatory process into phases, it observed that all LLs respected the sequence of phases, but not the planned timing for each. Phases 1 and 4 (Preparation and Evaluation) generally required more time than estimated (3 to 2 months extension). Conversely, the boundary between the two central phases (Planning and Implementation) was difficult to identify, and in many cases the intermediate event was postponed significantly, almost to the end of the participatory process.

ANNEX 1 – Stakeholders’ lists for each LL

This Annex contains the **lists of stakeholders defined by each LL** and revised at the end of the FEV project.

The lists for the five LLs are available as Excel files, attached separately to this document. In total, there are 5 files related to this Annex:

- The list of stakeholders of the Austrian LL;
- The list of stakeholders of the French LL;
- The list of stakeholders of the German LL;
- The list of stakeholders of the Italian LL;
- The list of stakeholders of the Slovenian LL.

ANNEX 2 – Interviews to LL Coordinators on the participatory process

This Annex contains the **interview form** and the **answers of LL Coordinators** during one-to-one meetings.

The documents are attached separately to this document. In total, there are 6 documents related to this Annex:

- Interview form;
- Interview to Austrian LL Coordinator;
- Interview to French LL Coordinator;
- Interview to German LL Coordinator;
- Interview to Italian LL Coordinator;
- Interview to Slovenian LL Coordinator.

ANNEX 3 – Stakeholders’ map and power/interest matrix

This Annex contains the **stakeholders’ maps and the power/interest matrices**, for each LL.

The documents are attached separately to this document. In total, there are 5 documents related to this Annex:

- The stakeholders’ map and matrix of the Austrian LL;
- The stakeholders’ map and matrix of the French LL;
- The stakeholders’ map and matrix of the German LL;
- The stakeholders’ map and matrix of the Italian LL;
- The stakeholders’ map and matrix of the Slovenian LL.

ANNEX 4 – Minutes of events held by each LL

This Annex contains the **minutes of events held by each LL**.

The documents are attached separately to this document. In total, there are 48 documents related to this annex:

- Minutes of the Austrian LL;

- Minutes of the French LL;
- Minutes of the German LL;
- Minutes of the Italian LL;
- Minutes of the Slovenian LL.

ANNEX 5 – Stakeholders’ satisfaction survey

This Annex contains the **form of the stakeholders’ satisfaction survey** and the related **answers collected**.

The documents are attached separately to this document. In total, there are documents related to this annex:

- Satisfaction survey form
- Answers for the Austrian LL;
- Answers for the French LL;
- Answers for the German LL;
- Answers for the Italian LL;
- Answers for the Slovenian LL.

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